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Highly pathogenic avian influenza in wild mammals: critical appraisal of spill-over events and of strategies for prevention, surveillance and preparedness

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Abstract

Recent years have seen an increase in spill-over events of Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) to mammals, posing a significant public health threat. This report examines the epidemiological drivers behind these events, the clinical and pathological features observed in naturally infected mammals, and the strategies for surveillance, control, and prevention. The study focuses on wild mammals in different settings, including sylvatic environments, farms, and zoos/rescue centres, highlighting the complexity of HPAI transmission from birds to mammals and potentially between mammals. Key factors influencing spill-over include bird migration patterns, shared habitats, mammalian diet and behaviour, and environmental contamination. Carnivorous mammals, particularly juveniles, are more susceptible to HPAI, with predatory and scavenging behaviours identified as critical epidemiological drivers. Outbreaks in farmed and captive wildlife are often linked to inadequate biosecurity and contaminated feeding practices. Surveillance efforts should integrate passive and active components, focusing on high-risk populations, and be linked to bird and human surveillance to effectively monitor and mitigate HPAI outbreaks. Control measures require a thorough understanding of transmission mechanisms, with specific protocols needed for different environments. Prevention strategies should emphasise biosecurity, carcass management, and communication efforts to foster effective outbreak management and preparedness.

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Key words: HPAI, bird flu, wildlife, interspecies transmission, one health

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Summary

Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza spill-over events to wild mammals have increased in frequency over the past few years, and the emergence of AIV capable of infecting mammals, including humans, is considered as a serious public health threat. This report aims to explore (i) the epidemiological drivers of such events, (ii) the clinical signs and pathology observed in cases of natural infection, (iii) surveillance and control strategies, as well as (iv) available tools for prevention and preparedness, by collecting information published in official reports and manuals of international or national organisations, as well as published literature. It will address three types of wild mammal scenarios, namely free ranging wild mammals in sylvatic environments or in anthropized settings, captive wild mammals in farms and captive wild mammals in zoos/rehabilitation centres. The transmission of highly pathogenic avian influenza viruses (HPAIV) from birds to wild mammals, and potentially between mammals, is influenced by a complex interplay of epidemiological drivers. Key factors include the circulation of specific HPAIV subtypes, bird migration and aggregation patterns (temporal and geographical), shared habitats between birds and mammals, and physiological, behavioural and ecological characteristics of mammal populations.

Bird aggregation plays a crucial role in the spread of HPAIV to mammals. HPAIV infection pressure from birds to mammals depends on how many birds are infected within an area and the timeframe of infection itself. Hot-spots for potential spill-over events are aggregation sites such as migration stopover sites, breeding grounds, or moult sites.

Mammals that share habitats with these birds, particularly in wetlands or semi-aquatic environments, are at higher risk of infection.

The susceptibility of mammals to HPAIV is also influenced by intrinsic susceptibility (Carnivora appear to be more susceptible to infection compared to other taxonomic orders), by their diet and behaviour. Predatory and scavenging habits especially towards birds, their carcasses, or eggs, are relevant epidemiological drivers.

Among the 51 wild mammal species affected by HPAIV since 2016, 44 belong to the order Carnivora and have a carnivorous or scavenging diet, highlighting the importance of dietary habits as transmission drivers.

Additionally, juvenile mammals appear to be more susceptible to HPAIV, possibly due to factors such as their immature immune system, and diet. This was evident in the high mortality rates observed in elephant seal pups during an outbreak in Argentina.

The presence of poultry or mammal farms infected with HPAI can serve as significant sources of infection for wild mammals, especially if biosecurity measures are inadequate. Overall, the epidemiological drivers of HPAIV transmission from birds to mammals are multifaceted, involving virus characteristics, environmental factors, and mammalian behaviours.

Understanding these drivers is essential for developing effective strategies to mitigate the risk of HPAIV outbreaks in wildlife and prevent potential spillover to humans.

Epidemiological drivers of HPAI spillover in captive species, particularly in farmed wildlife and animals in zoos or rehabilitation centres, are primarily influenced by biosecurity practices, feeding habits, environmental contamination, and proximity to HPAI outbreaks.

For farmed wildlife, the primary routes of HPAI transmission include contact with bird faeces and the consumption of infected animals.

Key drivers of spillover in these settings are biosecurity measures, feeding practices, and the farm's proximity to HPAI outbreaks.

The structure of farming facilities, such as open-sided cages that allow contact with wild birds, plays a significant role in the risk of HPAI transmission.

For example, outbreaks in fur farms in Finland and Spain were linked to direct contact with seabirds, facilitated by farm designs that exposed animals to wild (or domestic) birds.

Poor hygiene practices by farm operators, including improper handling of carcasses and feed, can also contribute to human-mediated transmission.

The use of contaminated equipment, vehicles, or feed, such as infected chicken meat, has been identified as a potential transmission route, as seen in outbreaks in China and Finland where infected meat was suspected to be the primary cause.

In zoos and rehabilitation centres, the drivers of HPAI spillover are similar but are influenced by the high density and close proximity of various species, which increases the challenge of avoiding contact with wild birds. Environmental contamination, particularly by bird faeces, is a significant concern, especially in facilities where animals are housed in open spaces.

Direct or indirect contact with contaminated environments, such as through water or food sources, can facilitate the spread of HPAI. Feeding practices are critical in these settings, as carnivores in zoos and rehab centres are often fed bird meat, which can transmit HPAI if infected (and not properly processed).

This was evident in multiple outbreaks, including in Thailand and Cambodia, where carnivores were infected after consuming contaminated chicken or wild bird meat. In some cases, feeding practices were adjusted after an outbreak, leading to a cessation of the disease, highlighting the role of feed as a primary driver.

Overall, the key epidemiological drivers for HPAI spillover in captive species revolve around the interaction between animals and potentially contaminated environments, inadequate biosecurity measures, and risky feeding practices. These factors underscore the importance of stringent biosecurity protocols, careful management of feeding practices, and monitoring of local HPAI outbreaks to prevent spillover events in captive settings.

An overview of the symptoms and main pathological findings was presented to provide the knowledge base necessary for an efficient application of surveillance measures distinguishing clinical signs reported in fatally affected animals with H5Nx which showed mostly neurological symptoms and also respiratory symptoms. Pathological findings have been reported, and while gross pathology is generally unspecific, involving mainly the respiratory system, histological lesions are mostly indicative of non-suppurative (meningo-)encephalitis, and frequently also (severe, acute) necrotizing non-suppurative interstitial pneumonia.

Surveillance programs for Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza virus (HPAIV) in wild mammals are essential for early detection, mapping outbreak distributions, and identifying emerging strains. Effective surveillance requires both passive and active components, to fully assess not only the component that might succumb to the disease (passive surveillance) but also that which survives and recovers. Both should focus primarily on high-risk populations such as wild carnivores and scavengers and aquatic mammals. At the same time, it should be kept in mind that knowledge on HPAIV in mammals in natural settings is still limited and in a situation of high infection pressure from birds, other mammal species may merit investigation to increase our understanding. The mammal component of the surveillance should also be

properly linked to surveillance in birds and humans and in order to be as efficient as possible an in-depth analysis of risk factors favouring bird to mammal spill-over and mammal to mammal transmission is needed and can be achieved with combined active and passive surveillance. To promote efficient surveillance for HPAI in mammals, in the case of passive surveillance, HPAI should be included among the surveillance targets in case of clinical signs (seen ante-mortem) or pathological lesions compatible with HPAI, animals that are found dead in proximity of confirmed/suspected cases of HPAI in birds, or mammals in at-risk epidemiological scenarios. Active surveillance is particularly recommended in high-risk scenarios to improve knowledge on ongoing (antigen detection) or past (antibodies) infection for sensitive species. Viral characterization by sequencing, is highly recommended for positive samples, to detect genomic adaptation to mammal hosts and potentiality of a zoonotic transmission. Control measures must be informed by a thorough understanding of the virus's transmission and maintenance mechanisms, although there is currently limited information on the epidemiology of HPAI in mammals. Specific protocols, similar to those used for avian hosts, need to be developed for mammals, considering the varied environments where outbreaks can occur, such as farms, zoos, and the wild. Biosecurity measures, including segregation, carcass removal, and disinfection, are critical, though more easily enforced in captive settings. Additionally, the management of HPAI outbreaks should involve careful transport protocols, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), and the monitoring of exposed humans for HPAIV associated symptoms. Continuous evaluation is essential to assess the effectiveness of these measures and to adapt strategies as needed.

Prevention of spill-over of HPAI in wild mammals requires enhanced surveillance, and biosecurity, especially in areas where birds and mammals congregate. Key strategies include ensuring biosecurity at sites where wild and domestic animals interact, such as fur farms, zoos, and rehabilitation centres. This involves segregating species, managing food sources to reduce risk, and designing landscapes to minimise contact between high-risk species. In sylvatic settings carcass removal, especially during mass mortality events, reduces viral load in the environment and exposure of mammals. Adequate legislation and a robust stakeholder network are crucial for effective outbreak management, while tools like national registers, previous knowledge on wildlife population (distribution and abundance), and predictive modelling can improve preparedness by identifying high-risk areas and guiding intervention strategies. Key communication strategies for managing HPAI include advocating for capacity-building in animal health communication, integrating strategic communication into national veterinary infrastructure and policies, and establishing an international network of experts in animal health and disease communication. Additionally, developing a communication action plan focused on H5N1 transmission, ensuring consistent and accurate messaging, and adopting a multi-sectoral and multidisciplinary participatory approach are essential for effective communication and fostering social and behavioural changes.

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1. Introduction

Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) viruses, traditionally associated with severe outbreaks in avian species, have increasingly demonstrated a capacity to infect a broader range of hosts, including various mammalian species. This expansion in host range is of growing concern due to the potential for these viruses to adapt to mammalian physiology, thereby enhancing the risk of disease spread among mammals and zoonotic risk. Recent reports have documented a rising number of HPAIV spill-over events in mammals, both domestic and wild. These developments necessitate a closer examination of epidemiological (and molecular) mechanisms behind spill-over events to wild mammals. The increasing incidence of HPAI in mammals underscores the importance of understanding the factors contributing to interspecies transmission and the potential public health implications. This report aims to present the latest findings on epidemiological drivers underlying HPAI in wild mammals both free-ranging and captive, analyse clinical and pathological signs in naturally infected wild mammals, which can be of use to develop and implement efficient surveillance schemes. The insights gained will be crucial for developing effective surveillance, prevention, and control strategies to mitigate the public health risks posed by these evolving viruses.

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor

As part of the specific contract 2, implementing Framework contract No OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01, the requestor specified the need for an appraisal of spillover events of **highly pathogenic avian influenza virus (HPAIV)** from birds to other mammalian species. The expected deliverables are a report and relative annexes are to be published in Zenodo.

Contractor: Enetwild 2.0 Consortium

Contract/Grant title: Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment

Contract/Grant number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01

1.2. Interpretation of the Terms of Reference

The Terms of Reference (ToRs) were interpreted as providing supporting information for efficient surveillance and preparedness for High pathogenicity Influenza A (HPAI) in wild mammals. Specifically:

- i.* to identify epidemiological drivers of HPAI in wild mammals based on spill-over events of HPAI virus to wild mammals (bird-to-mammal and mammal-to-mammal) in different epidemiological settings (free-ranging populations, wild mammals in farms, zoos and rehabilitation centres);
- ii.* to provide a summary of HPAIV clinical signs and pathology in naturally infected wild mammals relevant for risk-based surveillance;
- iii.* to critically examine the current surveillance and control strategies in the light of the identified drivers and disease manifestations;

to critically analyse the current prevention and preparedness measures to prevent spill-over events in mammals including humans.

1.3. Data sources and methods

Data sources

The primary data sources used for sections 2 and 3 were the EFSA reports on AIV present in PubMed and which mention 'mammal', as well as the ENETWILD 2024 report on HPAIV in mammals (Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024). Cited references were then further consulted (snowballing). The previous experience of the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza (IZSV, 2024a,b) and the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH, 2024a,b) were the main sources for the surveillance and control section (section 4). This information has been previously supported by previous EFSA/CDC and ENETWILD reports on HPAI infecting avian and mammalian species, respectively (EFSA, 2017, 2021; CDC, 2024a,b; Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024), as well as for several scientific publications covering this topic. In addition, the HADEA report (Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024b) was used for an overview of the national surveillance programs, as well as information obtained from the ENETWILD and the EWDA networks. Finally, for prevention, protection and preparedness (section 5), we used the latest WHO, ECDS and EFSA pertinent guidelines.

Definitions

We considered a **spill-over event** was any event of transmission of an AIV from a reservoir population, defined here as a population where this AIV is circulating, to another population where it was not circulating. This spill-over event could be followed by transmission in this second population or not. We defined the term **epidemiological driver** of HPAIV spill-over to mammals as a catalysing event for bird to mammal spill-over, or mammal to mammal spill-over of HPAIV. We chose this term over 'risk factor' or 'determinant' because most studies did not formally analyse the risk. We used the definitions of EFSA for **passive surveillance** (the reporting and investigation of increased mortality, other signs of serious disease or significantly reduced production rates with an undetermined cause in a targeted animal population) and **active surveillance** (measures initiated to detect and control animal diseases as early as possible using defined protocols and activities) (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/glossary>)

Methods

For driver identification (section 2), we scanned the data sources for examples of spill-over events to mammals. We assessed the circumstances described in each report to determine if they could be classified as drivers based on the authors' analysis and the hypothesized mechanisms of HPAIV transmission. For the latter, we used our understanding of HPAIV epidemiology, transmission dynamics and wildlife biology.

Similarly, the primary data sources were used to identify HPAIV spill-over events to mammals in which clinical signs or pathology or both were described. These were used for making an overview of the clinical signs and post-mortem findings in natural infections, reported where possible per species to detect differences if present (section 3).

After extracting the background for the surveillance and control section from the data from European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza and the World Organisation for Animal Health documents, the same approach was used to identify strategies implemented to control and prevent HPAIV events in wild mammals. We went through authors recommendations, which were compared to official guidelines to identify concrete examples for these as well. Where illustrative, examples provided in the responses from the ENETWILD and EWDA networks were used. For the last section (section 5), we compiled data from the aforementioned documents and guidelines to provide an overview of veterinary and public health system readiness and preparedness.

2. Identification of drivers of spill-over events of HPAI to wild mammals

2.1. Free-ranging wild mammals

Free-ranging wild mammals may be exposed to HPAI-infected birds or other mammals and the environment contaminated with their excretions and carcasses. Wild mammals that share habitat or feed on infected birds are prone to spill-over events (Root and Shriner, 2020, Leguia et al., 2023, Vreman et al., 2023). Airborne transmission seems to be of less importance for spill-over from bird-to-mammal (Vreman et al., 2023). Table 1 summarises epidemiological drivers for HPAI spill-over to free-ranging wild mammals.

Table 1. Epidemiological drivers for HPAI spill-over to free-ranging wild mammals, with underlying mechanism and examples

Epidemiological driver (Category)	Spill-over type and underlying mechanism	Examples (references)
Circulation of HPAIV subtypes/strains in birds that are more likely to infect wild mammals (<i>Virus</i>)	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal:</i> some HPAIV subtypes/strains may be more likely to cross species barriers and more likely to infect mammals than others. This observation was made for humans because outbreaks of HPAI H5N1, H7N7 and H7N3 in poultry were associated with probable infection in humans, but not H7N1 and H5N2 outbreaks (EFSA 2006, citing Hayden and Croisier, 2005).</p> <p><i>Mammal-to-mammal:</i> Within mammals, virus variants with mammal adaptations may develop that potentially enhance mammal-to-mammal transmission (Suttie et al., 2019). Even though there is no clear evidence so far that this led to mammal-to-mammal spill-over in the wild mammals.</p>	<p>The circulating HPAIV A(H5N1) clade 2.3.4.4b strains in birds have crossed many species barriers and have infected at least 51 wild mammal species (mostly free-living animals) since 2016 (EFSA Mar-Jun 2024, p22-25).</p> <p>Mammal adaptations have occurred in HPAIV A(H5N1) clade 2.3.4.4b strains in wild mammals, e.g., PB2-627K in wild red foxes (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>) (Vreman et al., 2023; Bordes et al., 2022; Chestakova et al., 2023; Elsmo et al., 2023; etc.).</p>

<p>Seasonal waterbird migration (<i>Bird</i>)</p>	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal:</i> The migratory movements of birds have been associated with HPAIV introduction into local bird and mammal populations (temporal considerations). In addition, at stopover sites, waterbird aggregation often occurs (see next driver).</p>	<p>The outbreak of HPAIV H5N1 subclade 2.3.4.4. in local bird populations with the spill-over to sea lions (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>) in Peru, followed the seasonal arrival of [infected] migrating waterbirds (Gamarra-Toledo et al., 2023; Leguia et al., 2023)</p>
<p>Waterbird aggregation (<i>Bird</i>)</p>	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal:</i> Virus circulation can be enhanced when high numbers of birds, infected and susceptible, aggregate. Intraspecies and interspecies aggregation of waterbirds occurs at migration stopover resting sites, at breeding sites, and sometimes at feeding sites, as well as at urban parks and ponds. Humans affect aggregation, e.g., by creating safe spots (protected sites) or artificial nesting sites (spatial considerations). At times, birds cannot leave aggregation sites (during breeding, during moult) (temporal considerations).</p>	<p>HPAI A(H5N1) infection was detected in 2006-2007 in Plateau pikas (<i>Ochtona curzoniae</i>) around Qinghai Lake, a waterbird aggregation site in China where HPAIV H5N1 was first introduced via migrating birds in May 2005 (Zhou et al. 2009) HPAI A(H5N1) infection was detected in 2024 in a Eurasian otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>) in a coastal area of Sweden where wild birds are abundant (EFSA, 2024)</p>

<p>High numbers of HPAIV infected wild birds (disease hotspots) (<i>Bird</i>)</p>	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal:</i> The level of exposure of mammals to HPAIV from birds depends partly on how many birds are (fatally) infected within an area and time frame, i.e., the infection pressure from birds to mammals. During HPAIV epidemics in wild birds, with HPAIV infection in massive numbers of birds, the level of exposure of mammals to virus will be high (temporal consideration), especially at disease hotspot sites (spatial consideration). Wild bird carcass removal at hotspots may reduce infection pressure among birds (Rijks et al., 2022, Knief et al., 2024) and subsequently to mammals.</p>	<p>HPAI H5N1 cases in wild mammals (Eurasian otter <i>Lutra lutra</i>, red foxes <i>Vulpes vulpes</i> and <i>Lynx lynx</i>) in Finland late 2021-early 2022 were spatially and temporally connected with mass mortality events in flocks of released pheasants (<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>), suggesting increased infection pressure from birds to mammals (Tammiranta et al., 2023, referred to in ENETWILD 2024). Natural infection with HPAI H5N1 virus in terrestrial wild mammals in the United States was concurrent with high levels of circulating HPAI viruses in wild birds during the spring and summer of 2022 (Elsmo et al., 2023) The sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>) die-offs in Peru was associated with a large biomass of infected wild birds (Gamarra-Toledo et al., 2023). An HPAI H5N1 outbreak in harbor seals (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>) and gray seals (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>) in New England (USA) was concurrent with a wave of avian infections in the region (Puryear et al., 2023). HPAIV H5N1 infection in a stone marten (<i>Martes foina</i>) in 2006 in Germany occurred in an area with numerous confirmed cases of HPAIV H5N1 infection in birds (on the island of Rugen in the Baltic Sea) (Klopfleisch et al., 2007)</p>
<p>Shared habitat with waterbirds (<i>Mammal</i>)</p>	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal:</i> Mammals living in waterbird preferred habitat (predilection sites) are more likely to encounter infected live or dead birds and virus</p>	<p>Sea lions (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>) that shared habitat with wild birds in Chile and Peru, were infected by HPAIV H5N1 (Ulloa et al., 2023; Gamarra-Toledo et al., 2023); phylogenetic analyses pointed towards transmission from avian</p>

	<p>in the environment contaminated by them. This is particularly present in wetlands and other (semi-)aquatic environments, but probably also other sites such as landfills (spatial consideration). Environmental persistence may differ among seasons (Mateus-Anzola et al., 2024) (temporal consideration)</p>	<p>sources (Pardo-Roa et al., 2023) (referred to in ENETWILD 2024). A wild mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>) infected with HPAIV H5N1 Clade 2.2.2. in Sweden in 2006 in an area with HPAIV H5N1 Clade 2.2.2. infected wild birds (Kiss et al., 2008; Root et al., 2020).</p>
<p>Life in aquatic environment (<i>Mammal</i>)</p>	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal</i>: If waters (and haul-out sites) are contaminated with HPAIV, mammals living in aquatic environments may be infected via water (both freshwater and marine waters). Because they live in the aquatic environment, not only their oral mucosae but all of their mucosae will be exposed to virus in water.</p>	<p>The confirmed case of H5N1 in a harbour porpoise, a species that does not feed on birds, for example strongly suggests that there can be a high enough infection burden of H5N1 in marine environments for spillover to mammals (Thorsson et al., 2023) (referred to in ENETWILD 2024). HPAI H5N1 infection of seals in New England (USA) likely occurred through environmental transmission of shed virus, because birds are not a typical food source for harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>) or gray seals (<i>Halichoerus grypu</i>) (Puryear, 2023) Four species of Delphinidae and 2 Phocoenidae, as well as 5 Otariidae, 4 Phocidae and 4 Mustelidae (Otters) species infected with HPAIV A(H5) clade 2.3.4.4b strains (H5N1 and H5N8) in nature (EFSA Mar-Jun, 2024, p22-25).</p>
<p>Having a carnivorous diet; scavenging (<i>Mammal</i>)</p>	<p><i>Bird-to-mammal</i>: There is a high risk of HPAIV presence in eggs and fresh carcasses (Serratosa et al., 2007). Mammals that feed off</p>	<p>Among the 51 wild mammal species affected by HPAIV since 2016, 44 belong to the order of Carnivora (EFSA Mar-Jun 2024, p22-25).</p>

	HPAIV-infected live birds, bird carcasses or eggs are prone to HPAIV infection. Some scavenging mammals could also be relevant as mechanical vectors; this has not yet been fully explored, e.g., for commensal rodents (Velkers et al., 2017).	
Mammal aggregation (<i>Mammal</i>)	<i>Bird-to-mammal & mammal-to-mammal:</i> When there are many mammals exposed to virus, there is a greater chance of a susceptible one being present, as well as more contact among mammals. High mammal density may also enhance susceptibility if associated with increased stress in individual animals due to factors such as mating or competition for food resources.	The 2023 sea lion HPAIV H5N1 die-off in Peru was associated with sea-lions (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>) aggregating for breeding (Gamarra-Toledo et al., 2023). Phylogenetic analyses of HPAI H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b. viruses obtained from sea mammals during epidemics at haul-out sites supported possible subsequent mammal-to-mammal transmission (Rimondi et al., 2024).
Being juvenile (<i>Mammal</i>)	<i>Bird-to-mammal:</i> Juveniles may be more susceptible. Also, lactating females and young animals may go for easy prey (sick or dead bird, that may be infected). <i>Mammal to mammal:</i> HPAIV infection is shed in milk and can be transmitted via milk. (temporal consideration)	62 of the 67 wild mammals (mostly red foxes) naturally infected by HPAI H5N1 from birds in the USA in Apr-July 2022 were juveniles (Elsmo et al., 2024). Mortality up to 95% in elephant seal (<i>Mirounga leonina</i>) was recorded in pups in Oct-Nov 2023 in Argentina (Uhart et al., 2024).
Proximity to farms with infected poultry or mammals (<i>Environment</i>)	<i>Bird-to-mammal or mammal-to-mammal:</i> Farms with infected poultry or mammals may act as	H5N1 infection in house mice on the premises of an infected poultry farm (EFSA 2024; https://www.cidrap.umn.edu/avian-

	<p>source of infection for free-living wild mammals if biosecurity measures are incomplete or virus poorly contained. For instance, farms with outdoor water facilities (Mateus-Anzola et al., 2024). Such risk can be greater in intensive farming areas.</p>	<p>influenza-bird-flu/usda-reports-more-h5n1-detections-mice-and-cats)</p>
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In examining the epidemiological drivers of HPAIV transmission from birds to wild mammals, and potentially between mammals, several key factors emerge. These drivers include the circulation of specific HPAIV subtypes, the impact of bird migration and aggregation in stopover (resting), breeding, feeding or nesting sites, the presence of disease hotspots, shared habitats between birds and mammals, and certain behaviours or characteristics within mammal populations. As an underlying epidemiological driver, **certain mammalian orders appear to be more susceptible** than others to infection (Enetwild et al., 2024). Spatial and temporal aspects must be considered, as fundamental for these drivers to occur and be relevant in an epidemiological setting. The propensity for spillover from birds to mammals is influenced by the specific HPAIV subtypes circulating in avian populations. **Certain subtypes**, such as H5N1, H7N7, and H7N3, have demonstrated a higher likelihood of crossing the species barrier from birds to humans compared to others like H7N1 and H5N2 (EFSA, 2006, citing Hayden and Croisier, 2005). This variation in interspecies transmission is likely due to differences in virus strains and their ability to infect new hosts. Evidence shows that certain strains, like the H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b, have crossed multiple species barriers and infected over 51 wild mammal species, mostly carnivores since 2016 (EFSA Mar-Jun 2024, p.22-25). For transmission among mammals, specific adaptations in viral strains that seem to occur in mammals, such as the PB2-627K mutation observed in wild red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*), could enhance mammal-to-mammal transmission, although this has not yet been conclusively proven in wild populations (Vreman et al., 2023; Bordes et al., 2022; Chestakova et al., 2023; Elsmo et al., 2023). **Migratory patterns of waterbirds** are another significant driver of HPAIV transmission. Migrating birds can introduce the virus to new regions, leading to spillover into local bird and mammal populations. For instance, the outbreak of HPAIV H5N1 in sea lions (*Otaria flavescens*) in Peru was temporally linked to the arrival of infected migrating waterbirds (Gamarra-Toledo et al., 2023; Leguia et al., 2023). Furthermore, the **aggregation of waterbirds** at migration stopover sites or breeding grounds can enhance virus circulation, increasing the likelihood of spillover to mammals. This has been documented in cases where mammals, such as Eurasian otters (*Lutra lutra*) and plateau pikas (*Ochotona curzoniae*), became infected in areas with high densities of infected birds (Zhou et al., 2009; EFSA, 2024). The level of infection with HPAI in birds is also a determining factor as the level of HPAIV exposure in mammals is closely related to the density of infected birds within a given area and timeframe. High infection pressure, particularly in disease hotspots, increases the likelihood of spillover events, as reported in the mass mortality events of wild birds in Finland and the subsequent infection of Eurasian otters (*L. lutra*), red foxes (*V. vulpes*), and Eurasian lynxes (*L. lynx*). This example illustrates how localised outbreaks in birds can lead to mammalian infections (Tammiranta et al., 2023; ENETWILD, 2024). Similarly, the die-off of sea lions in Peru and the outbreak in harbour (*Phoca vitulina*) or grey seals (*Halichoerus*

grypus) in New England were both associated with large numbers of infected birds, underscoring the importance of infection pressure as a driver of cross-species transmission (Gamarra-Toledo et al., 2023; Puryear et al., 2023). In conditions of high environmental contamination, mammals that share habitats with waterbirds, particularly in wetlands or other semi-aquatic environments, are at higher risk of encountering the virus. **Mammals with aquatic lifestyles, can be exposed to the virus via contaminated waters**, as documented in the cases of H5N1 spill-over in harbour porpoise (Thorsson et al., 2023; EFSA Mar-Jun 2024, p.22-25) and seals (Puryear, 2023). In particular, infection in the first species (harbour porpoise), which normally is not associated with birds' predation or haul-out sites, likely occurred through infected water. Fatal infection via contaminated environmental matrices, may be less frequent compared to infection via predation/consumption of infected birds, carcasses, or eggs. Among the 51 wild mammal species affected by HPAIV since 2016, 44 belong to the order Carnivora (EFSA Mar-Jun 2024, p.22-25). This high incidence of infection among carnivorous mammals highlights the importance of dietary habits and food preferences as a driver of virus transmission (Serratosa et al., 2007). Viral and bird-related epidemiological drivers should be considered along with mammal-related drivers. Age seems to be an important factor in determining mammals' susceptibility. Juvenile mammals appear to be more susceptible to HPAIV, possibly due to their immature immune systems and behaviours that increase their exposure to the virus. Notably, a significant proportion of HPAIV cases in wild mammals in the United States during 2022 involved juveniles, further emphasising the role of age and behaviour in virus transmission dynamics (Elsmo et al., 2024). Dependent young mammals may be exposed to the virus in milk from infected parents. Mortality rates up to 95% were recorded in elephant seal (*Mirounga leonina*) pups in Argentina during October-November 2023 epidemic, highlighting the vulnerability of juvenile mammals (Uhart et al., 2024). It should be noted that during epidemics, dependent young animals may also die indirectly from the disease by starvation, if the parents succumb to the infection.

The epidemiological drivers highlight the complex interplay between environmental factors, virus characteristics, and mammal behaviours in the spillover and potential transmission of HPAIV from birds to wild mammals, and from mammal to mammal. Understanding these drivers is crucial for developing effective strategies to mitigate the risk of HPAIV outbreaks in wildlife and prevent potential spillover to humans. In addition to the aforementioned drivers other factors that can play an epidemiological role include human-driven activities, such as deforestation and urbanisation that degrade and encroach on wild mammal habitat and contribute to increased interactions between domestic and wild species, influencing the transmission dynamics of avian influenza. Also, global trade and travel may facilitate the spread of AIVs, with infected avian and mammalian hosts potentially introducing novel strains to different regions (Enetwild 2024). These factors, although without direct circumstantial evidence for HPAI epidemiology in mammals are relevant drivers for the epidemiology of many wildlife-related diseases and should reasonably be taken into consideration also for HPAI.

The epidemiological drivers identified in section 2.2.1 were inferred directly from sylvatic settings, but they could also be considered as applicable to anthropized environments and to synanthropic wild mammals. In anthropized environments, natural ecosystems are altered, leading to changes in biotic composition, habitats and behaviour of wildlife, thus influencing ecological processes and disease dynamics. In anthropized/periurban settings, the local presence of poultry (or eventually mammal) farms infected with HPAI can play a particularly relevant role as source of infection for free-living wild mammals if biosecurity measures are incomplete or the virus is poorly contained. The risk is proportionally higher in intensive

farming areas (Mateus-Anzola et al., 2024). Information on wild mammal species to be considered in urban areas can be inferred from multiple sources including Enetwild Consortium et al. (2024) and Root and Shriner (2020). This last reference more broadly evaluated the potential role of synanthropic non-flying mammals as vectors of Influenza A viruses to poultry farms. Rodents, lagomorphs, procyonids, canids, felids, mustelids and artiodactyla should be considered when assessing HPAI in a synanthropic environment, for acquisition of mammalian-like adaptations and in the emergence of reassortant or zoonotic strains.

2.2. Captive wild mammals

2.2.1. Farmed species

Epidemiological investigations into spillover drivers in farmed wildlife should consider that the primary transmission route involves contact with bird faeces and the consumption of infected animals (ENETWILD Consortium et al., 2024). Specifically, three main areas of epidemiological drivers can be identified: biosecurity, feeding and proximity to HPAI outbreaks. To the best of our knowledge, spillover events to farmed wild mammals have involved fur animals such as red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*), arctic foxes (*Vulpes lagopus*), minks (*Neogale vison*), and raccoon dogs (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*) (Kareinen et al., 2024; Agüero et al., 2022; Qi et al., 2009) (Table 2).

Cages for these animals are often kept under open-sided structures, which have roofs but no walls thereby allowing contact with wild birds and their excrements. This was suspected as the main reason for two fur farm HPAI outbreaks: one in Ostrobothnia, Finland (Kareinen et al., 2024), and the other in Galicia, Spain (Agüero et al., 2023). In both cases, the structure of the farms permitted direct contact with seabirds. Other risk factors which can be inferred both from HPAI epidemiology in birds and from other wildlife-related diseases could have played a role in these outbreaks. Poor hygiene practices by farm operators (such as during carcass collection, feed processing, and use of disposable protective gear) were also established as relevant drivers for human-mediated transmission (Kareinen et al., 2024). Potential risk factors such as contact with contaminated fomites, including equipment or vehicles, or poor hygiene practices in feed management should be considered in analogous situations in order to better understand HPAI epidemiology in (wild) mammals. These potential risk factors were indeed evaluated in the Finnish outbreak but ultimately non considered as relevant drivers for the specific outbreak due to the pattern of disease incidents and the timing of infections (Kareinen et al., 2024).

Proximity to HPAI outbreaks is another critical factor for spillover, which can occur through two transmission routes: increased probability of direct or indirect contact with wild bird populations that may approach or fly over farms, as observed in Finland and Spain due to the presence of black-headed gulls and other seabirds (Kareinen et al., 2024; Agüero et al., 2022), and the use of infected meat as feed for farmed animals. While chicken meat was considered a potential infection route in two fur farms, one in Spain and one in China, this possibility was ruled out in Spain due to the absence of HPAI outbreaks in poultry in the region (Agüero et al., 2022). However, it was suspected as the primary route in China due to increased mortality of chickens, which were fed to raccoon dogs, in several backyard farms

at that time (Qi et al., 2009). In the Finnish outbreak the use of dead mammals (potentially already infected with HPAI) as feed for the same fur animals was investigated but not confirmed as a potential driver for between-farm transmission (Kareinen et al., 2024). No cases of HPAI have been registered in farmed wild ruminants or lagomorph species in Europe. However, recent outbreaks in cattle, sheep and goats (EFSA et al., 2024) have drawn attention on the spill-over risk to wild ruminants as well. Seropositivity has been reported in water deer (*Hydropotes inermis*) (Kim et al., 2018). Lack of biosecurity measures leading to contact with infected birds, fomites or high viral environmental pressure bird faeces, can reasonably be expected to be the main drivers for spillover to farmed wild ruminant species. Similar considerations may apply to the risk of spillover to lagomorphs: the case of detection of HPAI in plateau pika (*Ochotona curzoniae*) in China (Zhou et al., 2009) was the only report so far in the order while the Daurian pika (*Ochotona dauurica*) has been found positive for specific anti-Influenza A antibodies.

Table 2: Summary of epidemiological drivers for HPAI spill-over to farmed wild mammals

Epidemiological driver	Spill-over type and underlying mechanism	Examples with Reference
Open housing (biosecurity)	<i>Bird-to-mammal</i> : Fur animals are often kept in shadow houses, which have roofs but no walls. This setup allows direct contact with wild birds and their faeces, leading to HPAI transmission.	The farmed American mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>), infected with the HPAIV (H5N1) clade 2.3.4.4b genotype EA-2022-BB virus strain concurrently circulating in seabirds in the region, were farmed in a partially open building and may have been in contact with infected wild birds (Agüero et al., 2023)
Personnel (biosecurity)	<i>Bird-to-mammal & mammal-to-mammal</i> : Lack of biosecurity measures for animal workers, such as the proper use of clothing and protective gear when handling animals, carcasses, or feed, can carry the virus or feed, can carry the virus from infected farm animals to animals in other farms. Inadequate biosecurity measures when moving between farms can also contribute to virus spread.	Human-driven transmission probably occurred between 2 fur farms located 75 km apart. The farms had genetically closely clustered viruses and the same owner, who handled animals on both farms, did not change clothing between farms (Kareinen et al., 2024).
Bird meat feeding	<i>Bird-to-mammal</i> : Poultry meat or wild birds may be fed to farmed animals and, in some cases, serve as the main food	Poultry meat served as the primary infection source for raccoon dogs' outbreak in China (Qi et al., 2009).

	source, posing a risk for HPAI transmission.	
Species	<i>Bird to mammal</i> and <i>Mammal to mammal</i> : Carnivora appear to be more susceptible to infection compared to other taxonomic orders (Enetwild et al., 2024)	Out of 120 unique cases (records) of infection with AI of selected subtypes, 88.33% concerned the order Carnivora (other orders recorded were Artiodactyla, Didelphimorphia, Lagomorpha, Perissodactyla, Rodentia) (Enetwild et al., 2024).

Besides the confirmed epidemiological drivers there are a number of factors which currently find no hard evidence in HPAI outbreaks in captive wild mammals but that are reasonable to consider as potential risk factors (and have been evaluated in previous outbreaks). These potential risk factors can be assumed from the epidemiology of HPAI in birds or from other wildlife-related diseases:

- Proximity to outbreaks: possibly favouring transmission from birds to mammals, the presence of HPAI outbreaks in poultry or wild birds near farms or epidemiologically related outbreaks (e.g., in poultry farms supplying food for fur farms) increases the risk of transmission (Kareinen et al., 2024; Agüero et al., 2022)
- Proximity to wild birds: closeness to wild bird populations, particularly in wetlands and migratory hotspots, exposes farms to HPAI transmission (Kareinen et al., 2024).
- Presence of poultry on farm premises (biosecurity): in multi-species farming contexts, the presence of poultry can add an additional risk for disease transmission (Qi et al., 2009).
- Animal movements (biosecurity): The movement of live animals between farms, slaughterhouses, and trading sites can facilitate the circulation of the virus. Global trade is also considered one of the drivers that may contribute to the spread of spill-over events of HPAI to wild mammals (Kareinen et al., 2024).
- Equipment (biosecurity): Fomites contaminated by wild birds or other sick animals can be sources of HPAI transmission. However, the timing and pattern of infections should be considered to determine if this is the cause of an outbreak (Kareinen et al., 2024).
- Feed (biosecurity): feed can serve as the main source of infection either from infected poultry, or mammal meat. Post-production contamination through contact with infected birds is also possible (Kareinen et al., 2024; Qi et al., 2009).

2.2.2. Zoos and rehabilitation centres

Similarly, to farmed animals, epidemiological drivers for HPAI spill-over events in zoos and rehabilitation centres involve environmental contamination, feed and proximity to bird outbreaks (ENETWILD Consortium et al., 2024) (Table 3).

These environments are characterized by a high density of species living in close proximity, where avoiding contact with wild birds is challenging, especially when animals are housed in open spaces rather than cages (Bessière et al., 2024; Falchieri et al., 2024). This proximity

can lead to direct or indirect contact with contaminated environments, such as those polluted by bird faeces, ultimately facilitating the transmission of HPAI.

For example, during an HPAI outbreak among bush dogs (*Speothos venaticus*) in a wildlife collection in the UK, environmental samples and other animals in the park considered at risk were tested (Falchieri et al., 2024). However, while only one water sample from a drinking trough within the bush dog enclosure tested positive, this was not believed to be the primary source of infection, as will be discussed later. In a different case, involving a Tibetan black bear (*Ursus thibetanus*) in a French zoo, the most plausible route of infection was undetected viral circulation among the zoo's wild and captive bird populations (Briand et al., 2022; Bessire et al., 2024). The bear likely came into contact with an (alive or dead) infected bird or with food or water contaminated by avian droppings. Horizontal transmission was documented in some instances, such as the outbreak in a Thai zoo where tigers (*Panthera tigris*) became infected despite not being fed raw chicken carcasses, and no other avian or mammalian species in the zoo were affected (Thanawongnuwech et al., 2005). However, the possibility of mammal-to-mammal transmission remains under debate.

Overall, the primary epidemiological driver appears to be the consumption of contaminated bird carcasses. Carnivores in zoos and rehabilitation centres are often fed chicken or wild bird meat, which can transmit HPAI if infected. This mode of transmission was indeed hypothesised in the bush dog outbreak, where the animals were fed a diet that included frozen wild birds and game. In the absence of local disease events that could have been transmitted to the bush dogs within the enclosure, ingestion of infected meat or offal is the most likely source of infection. However, the wild game meat originated from a neighbouring estate with no reports of clinical signs or die-offs in local avian species (Falchieri et al., 2024).

In a separate outbreak in a Thai zoo, the animals were fed fresh chicken carcasses from a local slaughterhouse. At the time, chickens in the area were dying from respiratory and neurological symptoms later identified as H5N1 virus infection (Keawcharoen et al., 2004). In an outbreak at a Cambodian zoo involving several felid species (Asian golden cat *Catopuma temminckii*, clouded leopard *Neofelis nebulosa*, leopard *Panthera pardus*, tiger *Panthera tigris*), multiple sources likely introduced the HPAI virus, including virus-infected chicken used to feed carnivorous species, infected live chickens brought to nearby restaurants, and contact between infected wild and captive birds. The introduction through infected chickens was supported by the absence of an outbreak after feeding chickens to carnivorous species was discontinued, although deaths in domestic poultry continued in the area. Almost all carnivorous bird species died, as did most species typically fed chicken meat in captivity (Desvaux et al., 2009).

Also, two outbreaks of HPAI, one in zoo tigers in China and the other in wild civets in a breeding centre for a conservation programme in Vietnam, did not report feeding of dead poultry or birds, although isolate from the tiger's lung was phylogenetically almost identical to that isolated in the same year from a migratory duck at a nearby lake (Mustaq et al., 2008) and poultry deaths were reported in neighbouring villages to the second case (Robertson et al., 2009).

To accurately determine the origin of these spill-over events, an epidemiological analysis of HPAI outbreaks near the zoo or rehabilitation centre, including nearby farms supplying chicken feed, is essential. In some instances, the suspected source of an outbreak was either confirmed or ruled out based on the local epidemiological situation.

Table 3 Summary of epidemiological drivers for HPAI spill-over to captive wild mammals in zoos or rehabilitation centres

Driver	Explanation	Reference
Contact with wild or captive birds	<i>Bird to mammal:</i> Presence of susceptible bird species and proximity to mammal cages may increase the possibility of an HPAI outbreak	<p>Carcass of a black-headed gull positive for clade 2.3.4.4b H5N1 virus, was found in the enclosure of a Tibetan black bear (<i>Ursus thibetanus</i>) (Bessire et al., 2024)</p> <p>Presence of infective captive birds on the premises of a rehab centre contributed to infection spread among 5 of the 7 species of felids present (Desvaux et al., 2009)</p>
Environmental contamination	<i>Birds to mammal and mammal to mammal:</i> Contamination of feed or water sources	Water within bush dogs (<i>Speothus venaticus</i>) enclosure was found contaminated with H5N1 subsequent to first outbreak mortalities, from bird or from mammal origin (Falchieri et al., 2024)
Diet	<i>Bird to mammal:</i> Infected poultry or wild bird meat fed to animals may be the main source of HPAI	<p>66% mortality in bush dogs (<i>Speothus venaticus</i>) was caused by feeding on wild bird meat from a neighbouring hunting estate (Falchieri et al., 2024);</p> <p>Two tigers (<i>Panthera tigris</i>) and two leopards (<i>Panthera pardus</i>) in Thailand that were fed poultry were infected with same H5N1 strain concurrently circulating in poultry (Keawcharoen et al., 2004)</p> <p>Infected chicken meat used as feed for carnivorous species led to infection of lion <i>Panthera leo</i>, tiger <i>Panthera tigris</i>, Asian golden cat, <i>Catopuma temminckii</i>, leopard <i>Panthera pardus</i>, clouded leopard <i>Neofelis nebulosa</i> (Desvaux et al., 2009)</p>
Proximity to HPAI outbreaks	<i>Bird to mammal:</i> viral pressure by ongoing outbreaks in proximity of zoological collections or rehabilitation centers	Unexplained poultry mortality recorded at the time of outbreak in Owston's Civet in Cuc Phuong National Park,

		northern Vietnam (Robertson et al., 2009)
Contact with live poultry	<i>Bird to mammal:</i> presence of poultry on the premises	Live chicken kept on premises for human consumption led to infection of lion <i>Panthera leo</i> , tiger <i>Panthera tigris</i> , Asian golden cat <i>Catopuma temminckii</i> , leopard <i>Panthera pardus</i> , clouded leopard <i>Neofelis nebulosa</i> (Desvaux et al., 2009)

2.2.3. Considerations on HPAI adaptation for captive mammals

Characterising mammal mutations provides essential information to monitor viral evolution, to improve control and preparedness measures. In the past 4 years, of the 250 complete genome sequences of A(H5) viruses obtained from 17 different mammalian species in Europe, viruses belonging to 10 distinct A(H5N1) and A(H5N8) genotypes were identified. Even if most of the genotypes detected in mammals were initially also identified in birds (EFSA et al., 2024), genetic evidence shows that approximately 44% of these Influenza A (H5Nx) contain at least one of the adaptive markers associated with an increased virulence and replication in mammals within the PB2 gene (E627K, D701N, T271A or K526R) (Suttie et al., 2019; EFSA et al., 2024) and that these mutations have likely emerged upon transmission to mammals (Bordes et al, 2023) potentially posing a public health risk. For instance, recent outbreaks in Finland involving foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) and minks (*Neogale vison*) were linked to multiple introductions of the H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b virus, which had previously been detected in local wild birds and exhibited several adaptations to mammals (Kareinen et al., 2024). Within this outbreak, analysis of the intra-farm viral genetic diversity showed that viruses collected from 22% of the affected farms (6/27) did not show a genetic clustering within farm while viral samples collected from 11% of affected farms (3/27) formed well-defined separated clusters, strongly suggesting a single virus introduction followed by a within-farm virus evolution. Genetic analysis also showed evidence of spill-back to wild birds (Kareinen et al., 2024). Even if it specifically concerns domestic ruminants, in the recent outbreak with mammal to mammal transmission, the US H5N1 bovine isolate genotype B3.13, showed a mammalian adaptive marker PB2-M631L (detected in 99% of isolates) which has most likely developed after intramammary replication following a single introduction from birds and subsequent circulation within cow population (likely through cattle movement) (Halwe et al., 2024). Moreover, the NP gene that distinguishes the North American genotype B3.13 from all the other North American genotypes, may have resulted in a phenotype change that has likely favoured its spread in this new species (EFSA et al., 2024). This collective data underscores the significant genetic diversity of HPAI A (H5Nx) viruses and their increasing adaptation to mammalian hosts, raising concerns about potential public health implications.

3. Clinical signs and pathology of HPAI in naturally infected wild mammals

3.1. Clinical signs

Clinical signs in naturally infected, fatally affected, wild mammals are summarised per species in Table 4 and presented in detail in Appendix 1. In brief, HPAI H5Nx virus infection in the animals that died or were euthanized on welfare grounds was associated with principally neurological signs. Neurological signs described included ataxia, circling, paralysis, lack of fear of humans, disorientation, tremors, shaking and twitching, seizures, convulsions, spasms, opisthotonus, torticollis, stargazing, blindness, sialorrhea, as well as vocalisation and nystagmus. The most common general sign was lethargy, depression, and sometimes fever, unconsciousness or recumbency. Respiratory signs consisted of mainly dyspnoea, and sometimes also serosanguinous nasal discharge. Some aquatic mammals display only respiratory signs without neurological signs (Appendix 1). Diarrhoea is rarely mentioned.

There is no good insight into clinical signs of infected mammals that survive HPAIV infection in nature. Indeed, not all infected mammals die. Elsmo et al. describe two foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) that recovered in rehabilitation without any visible sequels (Elsmo et al., 2023). In addition, serological studies in stone martens (*Martes foina*) culled in the context of a meadow bird protection pilot, showed a significant proportion had antibodies against HPAI H5 viruses, suggesting these animals survived infection (Chestakova et al., 2023). It may be that survivors show less neurological signs during disease for example.

3.2. Pathology

Pathology in naturally infected, fatally affected, wild mammals are summarised per species in Table 5 (Gross pathology) and Table 6 (Histopathology) and presented in detail in Appendix 1. Animals were mostly in moderate to good condition (Table 5). The gross pathology reported may or may not be associated with HPAIV infection, as wild animals may also have other on-going infections, such as chronic worm infections. That said, in gross pathology the lungs showed most abnormalities (Table 5).

At histology (Table 6), most commonly animals presented with necrotizing non-suppurative / lymphoplasmacytic (meningo-)encephalitis, and frequently also (severe, acute) necrotizing non-suppurative interstitial pneumonia. The latter was not always associated with viral protein expression (Bordes et al., 2023; Mirolo et al., 2023)). Less frequently necrotizing myocarditis, hepatitis and pancreatitis and acute haemorrhages in organs were also observed.

Table 4. Clinical signs in wildlife naturally infected with HPAIV. Single species data is listed first, in alphabetical order of the family and then species. Results given for several species together are listed at the end of the table.

Species [Family]	General signs			Respiratory signs		Neurological signs								GI tract signs			Reference	
	Lethargy, depression	Fever	Other*	Dyspnoea	Serosanguinous nasal discharge	Ataxia	Circling	Paralysis	Lack of fear, disorientation	Tremors, shaking, twitching	Seizures, convulsions, spasms, opisthotonus, torticollis, stargazing	Blindness	Sialorrhoea	Other #	Inappetence, anorexia	Diarrhoea		Other
CANIDAE - Coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>)	x					x												Elsmo et al., 2023
CANIDAE - Gray fox (<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>)						x	x		x									Elsmo et al., 2023
CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	x	x	x	X		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Floyd et al 2021; Rijks et al 2021; Bordes et al. 2023; Elsmo et al., 2023; Erdelyan et al. 2024
DIDELPHIDAE - Opossum (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>)											x							Elsmo et al., 2023
FELIDAE - Bobcat (<i>Lynx rufus</i>)	x			X					x	x								Elsmo et al., 2023

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FELIDAE - Tiger (<i>Panthera tigris</i>)		x		X	x									x			Thanawongnuwech et al, 2005
MEPHITIDAE - Striped skunk (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>)	x			X		x			x	x							Elsmo et al., 2023
MUSTELIDAE - American mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>)	x		x		x	x			x			x		x			Aguero et al 2023
MUSTELIDAE - Eurasian otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)									x	x							Tammiranta et al. 2023
MUSTELIDAE - Fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>)	x					x		x									Elsmo et al., 2023
MUSTELIDAE - Stone marten (<i>Martes foina</i>)	x		x			x	x										Klopfleisch et al, 2007
OTARIIDAE - South American sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>)				x	x			x	x	x		x					Gamarra-Toledo et al, 2023; Rimondi et al., 2024
PHOCIDAE - Gray seal (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>)	x	x		x		x			x								Floyd et al 2021; Mirolo et al. 2023
PHOCIDAE - Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)	x									x							Floyd et al 2021; Postel et al 2021;
PHOCOENIDAE - Harbour porpoise (<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>)							x										Thorsson et al. 2023

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PROCYONIDAE - Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)						x													Elsmo et al, 2024		
VIVERRIDAE - Owston's civet (<i>Chrotogale owstoni</i>)								x			x							x		Roberton et al 2006	
Multiple species: CANIDAE, MUSTELIDAE & PROCYONIDAE - Farmed foxes (artic blue fox (<i>Vulpes lagopus</i>), the red (silver) fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), fox crossbreeds), mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>), and raccoon dog (<i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i>)	x			x		x												x	x	Kareinen et al., 2024	
Multiple species: DELPHINIDAE & OTARIIDAE - South American sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>), common dolphin (<i>Delphinus delphis</i>)				x	x	x	x			x										x	Leguia et al 2023
Multiple species: FELIDAE - Tigers (<i>Panthera tigris</i>),		x		x	x																Keawcharoen et al 2004

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leopards (<i>Panthera pardus</i>)																	
Multiple species: PHOCIDAE - Gray seal (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>) & Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)				x									x				Puryear et al 2023

*: Other general signs: malaise, recumbence, unconsciousness; reluctance to dive in a seal

#: Other neurological signs: Vocalisation; unspecified neurological signs

@: Other gastro-intestinal signs: Vomiting; unspecified GI signs

Table 5. Gross pathology in wildlife naturally infected by HPAIV. Single species data is listed first, in alphabetical order of the family and then species. Results given for several species together are listed at the end of the table.

FAMILY - Species	Body condition			Lungs							Brain		Other			Reference	
	Poor	Moderate	Good	(Dark) red	Congestion, hyperaemia	Haemorrhage	Heavy, swollen, oedematous	Pleural effusion	Poorly collapsed, diffusely firm	Mottled, marbled	Other #	Congestion	haemorrhage	Multifocal haemorrhages	Ocular discharge		Other @

HPAI in mammals

CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	x	x	x	x			x	x	x *	x						x	Floyd et al 2021; Tammiranta et al. 2023; Bordes et al. 2023
FELIDAE - Eurasian Lynx (<i>Lynx lynx</i>)		x		x			x			x				x		x	Tammiranta et al. 2023
FELIDAE - Tiger (<i>Panthera tigris</i>)					x	x		x			x						Thanawongnuwech et al, 2005
MUSTELIDAE - American mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>)				x		x			x								Aguero et al 2023
MUSTELIDAE - Eurasian otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)	x						x			x	x						Tammiranta et al. 2023
MUSTELIDAE - Stone marten (<i>Martes foina</i>)		x														x	Klopfleisch et al, 2007
OTARIIDAE - South American sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>)		x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x	x				Gamarra-Toledo et al, 2023
PHOCIDAE - Gray seal (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>)		x	x	x					x							x	Floyd et al 2021; Mirolo et al. 2023
PHOCIDAE - Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)		x									x	x				x	Floyd et al 2021; Postel et al 2021
PHOCOENIDAE -Harbour porpoise (<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>)							(x)										Thorsson et al. 2023
VIVERRIDAE - Owston's civet (<i>Chrotogale owstoni</i>)							x										Roberton et al 2006
Multiple species: CANIDAE & MUSTELIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), polecat (<i>Mustela</i>)				x					x	x	x					x	Vreman et al., 2023

HPAI in mammals

<i>putorius</i>), badger (<i>Meles meles</i>), otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)																	
Multiple species: CANIDAE, DIDELPHIDAE, FELIDAE, MEPHITIDAE, MUSTELIDAE & PROCYONIDAE - 1 coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>), 1 gray fox (<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>) 50 red foxes (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), 2 Virginia opossums (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>), 2 bobcats (<i>Lynx rufus</i>), 6 striped skunks (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>), 1 fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>), 4 raccoons (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)		x	x		x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x	Elsmo et al., 2023
Multiple species: FELIDAE - Tigers (<i>Panthera tigris</i>), leopards (<i>Panthera pardus</i>)								x						x			Keawcharoen et al 2004

*: when tested, not associated with virus protein expression

#: Pale foci; Nematode infestation with a variable associated subacute to chronic pneumonia

@: Other findings, most likely unrelated - Mild splenomegaly; Skin abnormalities (alopecia); blood-tinged transudate in thoracic cavity; empty stomach; dehydrated; mild swelling of the retropharyngeal lymph nodes; scattered pinpoint white foci in both kidneys; generalized lymphadenopathy; hyperplastic lymph nodes, moderate thymic atrophy, fibrinous perisplenitis and perihepatitis and catarrhal enteritis; Generalized lymphadenomegaly; pallor, congestion, enlargement, haemorrhage in the

HPAI in mammals

liver, congestion and cortical haemorrhage in the kidney, and pericardial effusion, petechia, myocardial pallor, GI tract: nematode parasitism, rarely congestion, haemorrhage, and loose faeces.

Table 6. Histopathology in wildlife naturally infected by HPAIV. Single species data is listed first, in alphabetical order of the family and then species. Results given for several species together are listed at the end of the table.

FAMILY - Species	Lungs							Brain			Other				Reference		
	(Severe, acute) necrotizing (nonsuppurative interstitial) pneumonia	Diffuse necrosuppurative bronchointerstitial pneumonia	Haemorrhage	Oedema	Hyperemia	Emphysema	Septal thickening	(Severe, acute), necrotizing nonsuppurative/lymphoplasmacytic (meningo)encephalitis	Suppurative encephalitis	Meningitis	Congestion	(Necrotizing) nonsuppurative/lymphoplasmacytic myocarditis	Moderate multifocal necrotizing hepatitis	Severe multifocal necrotizing pancreatitis in the pancreas		Acute haemorrhages in other organs	Other *
CANIDAE - Artic blue fox (<i>Vulpes lagopus</i>) [farmed]		x						x									Kareinen et al., 2024
CANIDAE - Red fox, silver fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	x							x				x	x		x	x	Floyd et al 2021; Bordes et al. 2023; Tammarinta et al 2023; Kareinen et al. 2024

HPAI in mammals

VIVERRIDAE - Owston's civet (<i>Chrotogale owstoni</i>)				x						x							Roberton et al 2006
Multiple species: CANIDAE & MUSTELIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), polecat (<i>Mustela putorius</i>), badger (<i>Meles meles</i>), otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)							x										Vreman et al., 2023
Multiple species: CANIDAE, DIDELPHIDAE, FELIDAE, MEPHITIDAE, MUSTELIDAE & PROCYONIDAE - 1 coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>), 1 gray fox (<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>) 50 red foxes (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), 2 Virginia opossums (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>), 2 bobcats (<i>Lynx rufus</i>), 6 striped	x						x				x						Elsmo et al., 2023

HPAI in mammals

skunks (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>), 1 fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>), 4 raccoons (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)																		
Multiple species: FELIDAE - Tigers (<i>Panthera tigris</i>), leopards (<i>Panthera pardus</i>)					X		X											Keawcharoen et al 2004

*: Other signs: Splenic lymphoid depletion; Peritonitis (in farmed mink); mild, eosinophilic, interstitial pneumonia (in the 2 common seals, consistent with lungworm infection)

4. Surveillance for HPAI spill-over events in wild mammals

Surveillance programs allow us to understand the epidemiology of transmissible diseases, monitoring the pathogen dynamics and favouring the implementation of prevention and control strategies (WOAH, 2024a). Current surveillance of HPAIV (Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza virus) in wild mammals is mainly aimed at the early detection of virus circulation, mapping distribution of HPAI cases and identification of emerging strains (Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024; EFSA, ECDC et al., 2024). For proper assessment, however, both on-going (antigen) as past (antibody) infections require investigation in mammals. This implies both passive and active surveillance components are needed. The mammal component of the surveillance should also be properly linked to surveillance in birds and humans. Inadequate monitoring delays outbreak detection, underreporting results and underestimation of spill-over events and, consequently, may make control measures inadequate (Singh et al., 2024; Shriner et al., 2016; Si et al., 2013). Furthermore, adequate communication and relations are needed between all surveillance components (mammals and birds, wild and domestic, humans) to better adapt and target surveillance.

An efficient way to find disease is to survey the animal populations that are most likely to be affected, i.e., to perform risk-based surveillance (active and passive are both viable schemes). This requires an understanding of risk factors and their impact on disease distribution (FAO, 2014). However, so far, there is a lack of studies that have formally identified risk factors and calculated or estimated relative risk values for HPAIV spill-over events to mammals (bird-to-mammal and mammal-to-mammal). In the meantime, surveillance schemes for HPAIV in mammals rely on mammal case / outbreak reports to identify epidemiological drivers, and on making parallels with known risk factors for birds, poultry and humans.

In the current mortality-based passive surveillance programmes, case detection has occurred mostly in wild carnivores and mammals living in the aquatic environment. These may have a higher risk of (fatal) HPAI infection compared to other mammalian groups, so the monitoring of HPAI in these species should be particularly attended (see section 2; Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024; Vreman et al., 2023). In some countries like Spain, the monitoring of wild carnivores (particularly foxes and wolves) is prioritised, along with farmed minks and pigs with suspicion to be infected by HPAI (MAPA et al., 2023). However, it is important not to neglect other species, as there are still many gaps in knowledge and the HPAIV situation in nature is/has been evolving rapidly. For instance, In addition to large- and meso-carnivores and mustelids, the French surveillance protocol also targets marine mammals and wild boars (Scoizec et al., 2024). So far only limited evidence exists regarding species-specific susceptibility and morbidity/mortality of viral genotype-host combinations in wildlife (EFSA, ECDC et al., 2024).

The potential involvement of HPAI infection in mammals during passive surveillance programs (examples in Table 7) should be considered in some epidemiological scenarios, among which the following stand out:

- Animals evidencing clinical signs compatible with HPAI. The identification of AI virus (AIV) infection based on the anamnesis is a challenge in the current epidemiological context of the virus circulation at a global scale. HPAI affects a wide variety of mammal species showing a vast diversity of clinical signs in each of them, ranging from asymptomatic infections to respiratory disorders or neurological manifestations, among others (Agüero et al., 2023; Englund et al., 1986). Nonetheless, clinical signs observed in the cases detected are mostly neurological signs, and in sea mammals also respiratory signs (section 3). Therefore, if mammals showed neurological signs ante-mortem, HPAIV should systematically be excluded by diagnostic testing in the current global context, at least when HPAI is circulating in wild birds or in poultry in the country or neighbouring countries. In at risk epidemiological settings, dead mammals with a history of abnormal behaviour should be fast-tracked for diagnostic testing. In sea mammals and some captive species, respiratory signs, particularly respiratory signs in certain population groups in which they are rarely seen (e.g., adult harbour seals), should also trigger diagnostic testing.
- Sick or dead mammals close to confirmed or suspected HPAI outbreaks in birds and/or mammals. This applies not only to captive settings (wildlife farms, zoos,...), but also to free-living wildlife. Indeed, high numbers of infected wild birds (wild bird disease hotspots) seem to be an important driver for infection of free-living mammals during epidemics, and mammal cases close to infected premises are highly relevant to test (section 2). As an example, the only red foxes that tested positive for HPAI in France (2023) were found dead in an area with ongoing massive mortalities due to the same virus in gulls.
- Animals showing another epidemiological connection with suspected or confirmed cases of HPAI in birds or mammals. It implies for instance mammals living in waterbird habitat, particularly those near waterbird aggregation sites (migration stopover resting sites, breeding sites, urban parks, ...), possibly intensifying surveillance effort around the time of the arrival of migrating waterbirds, during waterbird breeding periods, and (sea)mammal aggregation periods (see section 2). These epidemiological connections are relevant both in epidemic and in endemic situations. Geographically clustered cases of dead mammals should be investigated with high priority. In captive wildlife, environmental, biosecurity and feed connections should be kept in mind.

Dead mammals from the epidemiological scenarios ii and iii with non-suppurative (meningo-encephalitis or myelitis in histopathology (see section 3), in particular carnivores and aquatic mammals, may also be fast-tracked for diagnostic testing. Post-mortem examination must include histopathology, with analysis of adequately prepared brain tissue, as gross lesions alone cannot orient diagnosis (see section 3).

Table 7. Examples of epidemiological contexts where passive surveillance of HPAI in wild mammals could be performed in sylvatic environments, urban/periurban settings, farmed individuals and zoological institutions/rehabilitation centres.

	Example 1	Example 2
Free-ranging sylvatic environment	Mortality of wild mammals with history of clinical signs compatible with AI close to a natural park with a recent outbreak of HPAI in wild birds.	Neurological signs in wild carnivores in a region with a history of HPAI outbreaks in the same season during the last two years.
Free-ranging urban/periurban settings	Red foxes (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>) presenting neurological and respiratory disorders close to a periurban park where mortality in pigeons by HPAI infection has been simultaneously reported.	Mortality in free-ranging felids close to an urban pond with abundant presence of wild birds.
Captive farmed animals	Clinical signs compatible with AI in farmed wild ungulates housed near a poultry farm with recent HPAI cases.	Mass mortality in farmed mustelids where a relevant presence of wild birds (some of them dead) inside the facilities has been reported.
Captive zoos and rehabilitation	Mortality of yearling mammals in a zoo, close to facilities housing captive birds where confirmed HPAI infections have been recently reported.	Clinical signs consistent with HPAI observed in mustelids housed at a rehabilitation centre situated in an area where HPAI had recently been reported in wild birds.

Moreover, active surveillance of HPAI for monitoring the circulation of the virus in or via apparent healthy individuals is encouraged when potential risk factors for HPAI exposure are operating, particularly in high-risk areas or when passive surveillance is not efficiently settled. In this sense, two strategies may be followed:

- i. *Convenience sampling*: Collecting and testing samples from wild mammals to evaluate the exposure of these individuals to HPAIV (on-going or past infection). This *includes* sampling in live or dead mammals (e.g., hunted individuals, culled, live animals in conservation programs that are being sampled anyway for other purposes). Serological testing can provide valuable insights into the circulation of AI subtypes in the wild (EFSA and ECDC, 2024).
- ii. *Sentinel species*: Monitoring of selected animals periodically, to improve the early detection of virus circulation in mammals. For instance, in free-ranging species this can target at risk animals which might be early infected if a virus is to spillover to mammals (i.e. foxes which are carnivores and scavengers, easily found and abundant or otters in other settings).

HPAI was included in the list of cross-border pathogens that threaten the European Union which were addressed by coordinated surveillance systems under the One Health approach set up by Member States among the EU4Health Programme 2022 (Enetwild et al., 2024b).

Specifically, surveillance programs monitoring the circulation of HPAIV were set up in 11 European countries (Belgium, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Slovenia and Sweden), with the aim of early detection of pathogen emergence, followed by mapping distribution of cases/outbreaks, and finally, in countries where mammalian infections were recorded (or adjacent countries) the early detection of cases in mammals and of signs of viral mammalian adaptations. Surveillance efforts of Member States on mammal species are primarily focused on the active monitoring of terrestrial and marine carnivores, although some countries (Belgium, Germany, Ireland, Italy and Slovenia) also plan environmental surveillance (e.g., air and water sampling) at high-risk areas. Nine of the eleven Member States also planned passive surveillance programs in wild carnivores, while active strategies are only reported in two countries. Surveillance is reported to occur mostly in areas at higher risk (e.g. in areas of poultry outbreaks) in the majority of MSs, while only one country (Slovenia) reports a specific design for environmental monitoring of water bodies with sampling in stagnant and running water body types. Blood and tissue or organ samples are the main matrix implemented in the surveillance in almost all countries, while four countries (Ireland, Luxembourg, Slovenia and Sweden) do also include oronasal swabs. Sampling regimes include serology, immunohistochemistry, and molecular analysis of various matrices (blood/serum, cloacal and nasal swabs, and different animal tissues, highlighting the respiratory tract and central nervous system). Frequency of sampling is mostly unspecified, or sampling occurs when cases are suspected or mortality events in wild animals happen (passive surveillance). However, in Ireland foxes are sampled annually from September to December. All surveillance programs included at least one serological test, either ELISA or HI, and molecular analysis to characterise viral genotype (PCR or RT-PCR and sequencing) and detect potential evidence for mammalian adaptation. Additionally, Belgium and the Netherlands report to perform virus isolation in cell cultures. Croatia and Poland have not planned HPAIV surveillance in the framework, however, samples collected from wild carnivores/canids to survey other listed pathogens can be suitable to expand surveillance to HPAIV as well. Similarly, samples collected from rats and rodents in Belgium, Italy and Sweden (respectively for *Coxiella burnetii*, *Echinococcus* spp. and Tick-Borne Encephalitis virus surveillance) may also be tested for HPAIV (Enetwild et al., 2024b).

Basic epidemiological information from all the sampled animals is needed, which include at least animal location, date of sample collection, and species (Latin name), and preferably also age, sex, and clinical signs, number and species of other affected animals, among others (OFFLU, 2013).

The sampling of mammals for the HPAI surveillance mainly includes blood samples, brain and respiratory tissues in dead individuals. For instance, in several countries, sampling of dead mammals includes brain, liver, spleen and lungs, as well all macroscopically altered organs. Despite the lower sensitivity, oropharyngeal and rectal swabs can also be considered (WOAH, 2024b), with cautious analysis of negative results regarding the low sensitivity of those samples. Brain tissue, properly sampled to account for uneven distribution of the virus, is identified as the optimal sample matrix for reliable detection of the virus and should be prioritised when the number of individuals to be sampled limits the total number of samples that can be collected (Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024). At population level, less-invasive samples such as secreta and excreta or environmental samples may potentially provide

additional information regarding viral circulation at population level, and their use are currently being investigated (IZSV, 2024a; Duan et al., 2023). Investigation of mammals (e.g., rodents) for (mechanical) transmission might require taking other kinds of samples (i.e. environmental sampling on surfaces or feed) (Verkers et al., 2017).

All positive samples should be submitted for whole genome sequencing to characterise the molecular features of the predominant HPAI variant. The characterization of HPAI viruses using PCR (typing of Haemagglutinin (H) and Neuraminidase (N) genes) and sequencing should be a priority promoting the early detection and identification of new emerging HPAI viruses and viral adaptations or reassortments, which is of interest for public/animal health and biodiversity conservation (CDC, 2024; Leguia et al., 2023). Sequencing provides relevant information addressing evolutionary, clinical and epidemiological characteristics of circulating HPAI viral strains, so the quick deposition of sequences obtained on public databases (e.g., GenBank, GISAID EpiFlu, NCBI Flu Resource ...) will allow to improve proper surveillance and control strategies for animal and humans (OFFLU, 2024). In this line, the implementation of serological and anatomopathological studies are also highly encouraged (Duan et al., 2023). However, performance testing of serological analyses is currently being evaluated, so the results obtained should be cautiously interpreted (IZSV, 2024b). All the cases confirmed of HPAI infection in mammals should be immediately reported to the World Animal Health Information System (WAHIS) (WOAH, 2024a).

5. Outbreak control in wild mammals and prevention of spill-over events to mammals

5.1 Outbreak control in wild mammals

The management of HPAI outbreaks in wild mammals requires a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach integrating not only the monitoring of virus circulation in all sectors at risk, but also the implementation of control strategies in collaboration with official institutions at national and international scale. It is essential to develop specific and detailed protocols focused on the control of the virus circulation in mammals, similar to those previously reported in avian hosts (EFSA et al., 2021). Such protocols should be developed in close collaboration with the wildlife stakeholders concerned by the different epidemiological scenarios. This may require amending legislation, as for the control of HPAIV in mink fur farms in Finland (Lindh et al 2024).

The great variability of epidemiological scenarios in which HPAI outbreaks can occur (e.g. wild environments, farms, zoos, etc.) strongly influences the control strategies to be followed in mammals. The application of control strategies needs a preliminary identification of the mechanisms involved in the maintenance and transmission of the virus. Despite the recent impact of HPAI outbreaks in mammals worldwide, there is a lack of information about the epidemiology of AI in mammal species. The exact measures applied to control an outbreak of HPAIV in mammals are also often poorly documented, with some exceptions (Lindh et al., 2024). Therefore, some of the proposed measures are based on experience

with HPAIV control in poultry and, for free-living wildlife, on control of other notifiable diseases.

Identifying outbreak area

Passive and active surveillance (diagnostic testing) in the outbreak location and beyond is essential to determine the outbreak area. Additionally, for captive wildlife, reporting of sick animals and mortality changes with a low threshold may be promoted (Lindh et al. 2024). There is a need to assess with the stakeholders the advantages and disadvantages of using rapid tests, and to explain the importance of continuing to submit samples to surveillance programs (laboratory testing and sequencing).

Biosecurity

The implementation of biosecurity measures can help to reduce the impact of HPAI in susceptible mammal populations. After confirming a HPAI outbreak (or sometimes already upon strong suspicion), several biosecurity strategies should be considered, including segregation, removal of sources of infection, cleaning and disinfection (EFSA et al., 2017; FAO, 2009). Measures such as segregation, cleaning and disinfection can be more easily implemented in captive settings than in nature.

Segregation refers to the creation and maintenance of physical barriers (e.g., installation of meshes, keeping susceptible mammals inside facilities...) to avoid or limit the contact between infected animals or materials with non-infected individuals, which could prevent many new HPAI infections. Segregation in free-ranging wildlife involves compartmentalisation of populations. In captive facilities, physical barriers should be considered both for birds and mammals.

Regarding cleaning and disinfection programs in captive settings, these measures cover the removal of visible dirt in the first term (e.g., faeces, carcasses...) and then, the inactivation of viable viruses applying disinfectant products whenever possible, such as in zoological institutions or rehabilitation centres. These interventions not only include the environment of infected animals, but also the equipment and vehicles used. Strategies to avoid infection spread through waste and fomites should be made, as done in the 2022 HPAI outbreak on a mink farm in northern Spain (Agüero et al., 2023). When done in nature, management of waste waters and choice of disinfectants must be considered to protect the surrounding environment and wildlife (Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, fisheries and food, 2024).

In any case, people involved in the management of confirmed or suspected AI outbreaks must be appropriately equipped and trained in general biosecurity measures and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), avoiding the contact with infected animals and other potential infective sources (e.g., faeces, litter, raw milk, surfaces and water...) (CDC, 2024; WOH, 2024b). Despite the use of PPE, people exposed to HPAI should be monitored for the appearance of clinical signs (including respiratory or ocular signs) up to 10 days after their last exposure to HPAI (CDC, 2024) (see section 6).

For outbreak control in captive contexts and for synanthropic wildlife, special attention should be given to limiting the attractants for mammals (e.g. animal by-products, waste...) and efficient rodent control should be in place (Shriner et al., 2016, Velkers et al. 2017).

Culling (or removal for recovery)

In some situations, it may be advisable to cull the sick animals (and sometimes also apparently healthy susceptible animals that share premises) for mitigating the animal suffering and/or preventing the transmission of HPAI to non-infected individuals (WOAH, 2024b). Culling has been applied in HPAI outbreaks on fur farms in Spain and Finland (Agüero et al., 2023; Lindh et al 2024). In Finland, this could be culling of all fur animals on the premises or a subset (Lindh et al, 2024). However, in other epidemiological scenarios, before deciding on such measures, consideration should be given to the fact that some animals can survive infection and that survivors contribute to group immunity. Also, the conservation status of the affected species should be heeded (minimise the culling of endangered species). Guidelines for proper isolation during recovery are then needed.

Vaccination

Vaccination may in principle be part of the control measures. See section on prevention.

Evaluation of control measures

The application of control measures requires periodic surveillance to evaluate their effectiveness. This issue allows the implementation of modifications in control actions based on surveillance findings. The World Organisation for Animal Health recommends avoiding the application of unnecessary trade restrictions, unless scientific and technical information supports these measures (WOAH, 2024a).

Table 8 Examples of control practices for different wild mammal categories

	Identifying outbreak area	Biosecurity	Culling or isolation	Vaccination
Free-living wildlife, including synanthropic wildlife	Passive and active surveillance (diagnostic testing) in and beyond outbreak area	Compartmentalisation, use of PPE, if disinfect consider environmental impact of product	In case of localised mammal-to-mammal transmission, focal culling to be considered (or isolation of sick animals, especially if of conservation value). Of limited value in marine mammals.	

Farmed wildlife	Reporting of sick animals and mortality changes even with low threshold	Physical barriers, cleaning and disinfection of premises, equipment vehicles, removal waste, fomites and attractants, efficient rodent control, use of PPE	Culling of all or a subset of animals on the premises to stamp out the outbreak.	
Zoo/rehab	Passive (and active) surveillance in and beyond affected enclosures. Testing of environmental samples.	Physical barriers, cleaning and disinfection of premises, equipment vehicles, removal waste, fomites and attractants, efficient rodent control, use of PPE	If conservation value, proper isolation during attempted recovery.	Option to be explored.

5.2 Prevention of spill-over to wild mammals

Biosecurity guidelines have been produced by national (USDA, APHIS) or international (FAO, WOA) organisations. Some examples can be found at: [APHIS – factsheet on wildlife biosecurity](#), [USDA’s Defend the Flock outreach campaign](#), [CDC recommendations on potential biosecurity solutions](#)

Additionally, manuals on biosecurity and preparedness for HPAI in birds produced by international organisations such as FAO regarding birds should be carefully considered and, where possible, applied to wild captive mammals too (Martin et al., 2009; FAO 2008). Biosecurity can be also extended to wildlife handlers to prevent transmission from wild birds to wild mammals (either free ranging or captive) (World Organization for Animal Health’s Working Group on Wildlife, 2022).

Prevention of infection introduction

Regarding practices focused on reducing infection sources, the removal of carcasses from the environment stands out (Enetwild Consortium et al., 2024, WOA, 2024). The management of infected carcasses (bird and mammal) must be supervised by the competent authorities to assure the application of international guidelines and local health and environment regulations during removal and disposal (WOA, 2024b; Miller et al., 2020). In nature, carcass removal should be considered with cautions evaluating the risk/benefit ratio. For instance, invasive interventions such as carcass removal carried out within a breeding colony may lead to stress and disturbance, which in turn may enhance disease spread over a wider area.

Management of potentially contaminated fomites or other environmental sources (i.e. rodents and pests, water) is also to be taken into account. For instance, contamination of fomites and the environment by sick or dead birds was deemed the initial driver for the outbreak in fur farms in Finland (Kareinen et al., 2024).

In carnivorous species, the consumption of bird meat, whether from poultry or wild birds, is the most common route of infection with HPAI (Falchieri et al., 2024; Qi et al., 2009; Mushtaq et al., 2008; Thanawongnuwech et al., 2005; Keawcharoen et al., 2004). This is particularly concerning in settings like fur farms, zoos, and rehabilitation centres, where poultry or other birds often constitute a primary food source for these animals. In fur farms, also fur animal carcasses can be fed (Kareinen et al., 2024). In the presence of HPAIV, given the high risk of HPAI transmission through contaminated meat, it is essential to evaluate and consider alternative food sources that do not carry the same level of risk. Alternatively, measures should be taken to inactivate HPAIV in the carcasses. In a Cambodian zoo, where 9 species of felids were infected with HPAIV, meat of chickens from local farms was identified as the source of infection (Desvaux et al., 2009).

Prevention of spread by species separation

Physical barriers can be considered for both bird and mammal sources of spill-over events. Within poultry farms, segregation measures include physical limitation of wild mammals to farm premises. Physical barriers also effectively apply to facilities hosting mammals to prevent mammal-to-mammal spillover. In captive settings, rodents have been hypothesised to be efficient mechanical vectors (for bird to mammal transmission and mammal to mammal). The implementation of effective rodent control measures including reduction of food resources, water, shelter and nesting places available to rodents, can limit viral circulation and spread (Shriner et al., 2016; Velker et al., 2017).

In the context of captive mammals, it is advisable to minimise contact between different species to prevent spill-over events (Qi et al., 2009; Desvaux et al., 2009). Chickens, originating from local farms, and kept alive on zoo premises for human consumption were identified as a source of HPAIV infection for felids (Desvaux et al., 2009). Species separation can be achieved through strict biosecurity measures designed to keep species separate or by avoiding the co-habitation of multiple species within the same facility. Particularly, it is important to prevent the housing of high-risk species, such as poultry or waterfowl, alongside mammals whenever possible.

Prevention of spread through diseased animals under treatment

In rehabilitation centres, zoos or veterinary practices where wildlife is treated, in order to limit the geographical expansion and zoonotic implications of HPAI, preventive measures should be applied when HPAI is present in nature. It is suggested that the transport of wild animals suspected to be infected with HPAI to rehabilitation centres must be prevented for preserving the health status of other captive specimens (WOAH, 2024b). When transport does occur, adequate biosecurity measures must be in place during the transport to facilities, where the

animal can be humanely euthanized or be placed in quarantine for possible recovery. Animal ambulances and rehabilitation centres may require support to properly implement adequate biosecurity measures, and rehabilitation centres for to developing appropriate quarantine facilities (without any link with the rest of the facility, including specific persons for operating the quarantine), as well as proper quarantine and testing procedures for HPAI high-risk species. In principle these persons should not have direct interactions with birds or mammals for at least two weeks after being in contact with HPAI-infected animals (WOAH, 2024b). In practice, this may be difficult to adhere to, for instance in a rehabilitation centre, because during HPAI outbreaks in nature, wild animals continue to be submitted. However, strict separation of teams working in the quarantine facilities and in the remainder of the rehab centre can be achieved.

Landscape design

Human activities are affecting animals interaction at the bird-mammal interface, involving changes on habitat fragmentation patterns, creation of areas with high population densities (both for humans and wildlife), the displacement or the destruction of food sources, with consequent displacement and aggregation of wild species and an increased contact rate between wild mammals and bird species. Of particular interest are hotspots such as waste disposal sites, which attract scavenger mammals, among the species with the highest risk of spill-over because of their feeding habits, and artificial water bodies, which can congregate waterfowls together with wild mammals. Careful landscape design may help protect from HPAI spill-over.

Evaluation of preventive measures

It is important to evaluate the effectiveness of the measures for prevention of spill-over to mammals. For example, during mass mortality events in birds, it is perceived that bird carcass removal is likely to limit exposure and spill-over of mammals. Research (preferably case-control design) is needed to scientifically support this effort. Research can also address prevention strategies that have not yet been explored, e.g., water management strategies (pathogen dilution).

Table 9 Examples of prevention tools for different wild mammal categories.

	Biosecurity	Food sources	Species separation	Landscape design
Free-living wildlife, including synanthropic wildlife	Biosecurity for wildlife handlers	Carcass removal		Water bodies, habitat fragmentation, waste disposal sites

Farmed	Biosecurity practices for animal handling, feeding, equipment/workers	Consider alternative food sources to poultry/wild birds	Avoid poultry on the farm	Avoid location in proximity to wild birds gathering sites, wetlands, water bodies
Zoo/rehab	Quarantine, biosecurity practices for animals handling, equipment, PPE, spatial planning	Consider alternative food sources to poultry/wild birds	Avoid contact between mammals and HPAI bird reservoir species	Avoid locations in proximity to wild birds gathering sites, water bodies

5.3 Preparadness tools

Stakeholder networks

An outbreak of HPAI in wild mammals involves a complex network of stakeholders, each playing a crucial role in managing the crisis. These stakeholders include various ministries, veterinary authorities, nature managers, hunters, farmers, and associations representing those who work in zoos and rehabilitation centres. Given the diverse needs of these groups, it is essential to consolidate and strengthen these networks to ensure efficient communication, coordination, and action during an outbreak. By fostering closer collaboration and clear channels of communication among these parties, responses can be more unified and effective. This includes sharing timely information, coordinating on-the-ground actions, and aligning on best practices for biosecurity and containment. Strengthening of these networks not only enhances the immediate response to an outbreak but also builds a more resilient framework for future challenges, ensuring that all involved parties are prepared to act swiftly and cohesively to protect both animal and public health. Regarding captive settings, Finnish health authorities organised weekly meetings with relevant stakeholders to ensure flow of communication and support (Kareinen et al., 2024).

Legislation

Effective legislation plays a critical role in enabling governments to swiftly and decisively respond to outbreaks, particularly in the context of farmed animals. Given the high density of animals in farming environments, the risk of disease spread is significantly amplified, making it essential for governments to have the legal authority and frameworks in place to implement rapid containment measures. Adequate laws and regulations can facilitate actions such as mandatory quarantine, culling of infected or exposed animals, and the enforcement of biosecurity protocols. Furthermore, well-crafted legislation can ensure that appropriate resources are allocated for outbreak management, support the coordination between various governmental and non-governmental agencies, and provide clear guidelines for farmers and industry stakeholders. In the case of the HPAI outbreak in Finnish fur farms, to provide a legal

framework for veterinary authorities to control HPAI on fur farms and protect humans from infection, the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry reclassified HPAI in fur animals from notifiable diseases to other diseases to be combated (Kareinen et al., 2024). This allowed them to impose restrictions on farms, such as forbidding animal movements to and from the affected farms, carry out epidemiological surveys and trace contact farms for sampling. In addition, this gave the Finnish Food Authority the legal authority to cull animals on infected farms and the owners were entitled to governmental compensations for the financial losses.

Wildlife distribution

National registers of captive wildlife facilities - Preparedness strategies for managing a HPAI outbreak must be grounded in an understanding of the captive wild animal populations within the territory of interest. Effective action to contain an outbreak, as well as the development of robust surveillance plans, requires detailed information about the number, size, and location of farms, as well as the diversity and grouping of species within these facilities. Similarly, comprehensive knowledge of zoos, wildlife parks, and rescue centres, including the spatial distribution of these facilities and the species present, is crucial. This data allows for more precise targeting of biosecurity measures, rapid response planning, and the efficient allocation of resources during an outbreak.

Knowledge of wildlife species distribution and abundance -Additionally, an important tool to improve preparedness would be to map wild birds distribution, densities and movements with respect to wildlife captivity sites (farms, zoos, rehabilitation centres, ...) and free-ranging populations. Knowledge on distribution and abundance of free-ranging mammal populations is key to identifying risk scenarios (with reference to geographical and temporal settings).

Predictive models

Predictive models are valuable for informing prevention and control strategies by identifying when and where the risk of spill-over is highest (Prosser et al., 2024). While current research focuses on the wild-domestic bird interface, modelling risk of spill-over to wild mammals poses additional challenges. This requires a deeper understanding of HPAI spill-over to mammals, ecological interactions between birds, environment and mammals, and transmission dynamics, which remain complex and not fully understood. Given the incidental occurrence of most spill-over events, harmonised collection of spill-over epidemiological data should be collected at European scale to provide informative data points for models.

Table 10: Preparedness tools for different wild mammal categories

	Stakeholders network	Legislation	Wildlife distribution	Predictive models
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Free-living wildlife, including synanthropic wildlife	Hunters, wildlife managers, forestry ministry, veterinary authority		Access to knowledge on distribution and abundance of wild birds and free-ranging mammal populations over time	Risk models for spill-over events in wild mammals
Farmed	Farm workers and owners, feed producers, ministry of agriculture and veterinary authorities, farm veterinarians	Legislation to streamline animal sacrifice	Captive wild animals' farms (and biosecurity measures) with number of animals housed, neighbouring poultry farms. Mapping of wild bird distribution, abundance and movements with respect to farms	Risk models for spill-over events in wild mammals
Zoo/rehab	Workers, managers, zoo veterinarians, wildlife rehab centres managers, animal ambulance managers, veterinary authority		Registry of animals and species held in the structure	Risk models for spill-over events in wild mammals

6. Prevention and preparedness measures for zoonotic risk associated with HPAI in wild mammals

The current advice from WHO and ECDC about the risk associated with the recently reported A(H5) clade 2.3.4.4b viruses currently circulating in Europe, as well as for HPAI A(H5N1) viruses infecting humans, is low for the general population and low-to-moderate for occupationally exposed individuals (WHO, 2022a, b, 2023, ECDC, EFSA and EURL, 2023a, ECDC, 2019). The risk is considered low-to-moderate for people who are occupationally or otherwise exposed to birds or mammals infected with avian influenza. (EFSA, 2022, EFSA, 2024, ECDC, 2023b).

In this section we briefly provide insight on communication guidelines, general measures to reduce zoonotic transmission risk and related personal protective equipment, together with vaccination and post-exposure measures and generation of sequencing data as based on the

latest WHO, ECDS and EFSA guidelines. An overview of pertinent legislation on occupational health and safety is also provided.

6.1 Communication guidelines

International organisations such as FAO and WOAHP have produced several guidelines for risk communication in animal disease outbreaks and emergencies, including HPAI specific strategies in birds (FAO/WOAH International Animal Health Communicators' Roundtable; 2007; WOAHP, 2024). For a successful and balanced communication:

- Ensure use of scientifically accurate, referenced information.
- Seek technical review
- Use matter-of-fact language without hyperbole.
- Provide context for quotes, claims or research findings.
- Emphasise the ecological and economic benefit and importance of wildlife.
- Promote co-existence with wildlife.
- Address and dispel misconceptions and myths.
- Ensure any photos of people handling wild animals show correct use of PPE.
- Provide advice and language tailored to different stakeholder groups (WHO, 2024).

The general public and stakeholders need to be regularly informed about HPAIV and why control measures are necessary and the exact function of each of these measures. Informed citizens can better understand and support government actions like culling to control outbreaks. Communication to higher risk groups includes information on how to properly handle animals, disinfect equipment, control the movement of people and animals, and respond to potential signs of an outbreak.

Examples of governmental websites including information on HPAI spill-over in mammals include [Spain](#), [Finland](#), and [Switzerland](#).

6.2 General measures to reduce human risk of exposure to avian influenza

General literacy on basic biosecurity measures when in contact with wildlife is needed. Overall (inter-)national websites indicate the general public should avoid contact with sick or dead wild animals susceptible to avian influenza and, if they find dead animals, inform relevant authorities to ensure safe removal and further investigation, if required. As they may still handle sick or dead animals, they should also have access to information on how to maintain biosecurity to reduce zoonotic risk.

Appropriate personal protective equipment should be used to reduce the risk of infection when in contact with potentially infected animals or highly contaminated environments (see details in section on PPE).

Information should be provided to raise awareness among people at potential risk of exposure on how it can be mitigated. Guidance tailored to specific occupational groups, or people engaged in recreational activities where additional measures may be beneficial, should be provided.

6.3 Personal protective equipment (PPE)

Direct and unprotected exposure to possibly infected poultry or wild animals and their bodily fluids (including faeces and blood) are the most likely source of infection for humans. Adhering to biosecurity, including wearing personal protective equipment (PPE), is therefore recommended to decrease the individual risk of infection.

In general, sick and dead wild mammals should not be touched without proper precautionary measures such as wearing gloves, at the minimum.

In the EU/EEA, occupationally exposed people involved in control measures during an avian influenza outbreak, such as cullers, farmers and veterinarians, and staff at zoos and rehabilitation centres, with direct contact to infected animals and highly contaminated environments, are considered being at a higher level of risk. They should be adequately trained, and proper gear should be made available. Also workers in close contact with potentially infected mammals such as minks, foxes or other wildlife (for e.g. at rehabilitation centres or in areas with high level of avian influenza outbreaks in wild birds), and other groups of people such as backyard farmers or wild bird hunters with possible exposure to infected poultry, wild birds or wild mammals (mainly carnivores) should use PPE and trained on avian influenza as well as the possible risks associated with direct and unprotected contact.

Recommended personal protective equipment (PPE):

- Well-fitting filtering face piece class-2 mask (FFP2) or respirator ;
- Goggles;
- Disposable gloves or thicker rubber gloves that can be disinfected;
- Coverall or full body suit that can be disposed or washed and disinfected;
- Boots that can be cleaned and disinfected according to the national or local guidance.

In addition, other equipment such as an apron can be considered. PPE should be provided in different sizes as appropriate. Respirators have limitations for persons with different face shapes or facial hair. If respirators do not fit well, then the use of positive-pressure respirators should be explored. Staff should be trained to don (put on) and doff (put off) the PPE appropriately.

Data show that ocular conjunctival inoculation of seasonal and avian influenza viruses in ferrets can lead to productive and transmissible infection. Viruses can then be shed via direct contact or through aerosol. This underlines the importance of protecting the eyes and using goggles when in contact with infected animals, particularly related to occupational or culling activities where contaminated dust particles could enter the eye (ECDC Protective measures and options for public health response for avian influenza).

6.4 Vaccination for avian influenza (europa.eu)

Vaccination against seasonal influenza can be offered to individuals who are occupationally exposed to avian influenza to reduce the risk of reassortment between avian and human influenza viruses. Furthermore, vaccination against A(H5) virus can be considered for protection of those at higher risk of exposure to A(H5N1) as a component of a wider, comprehensive approach to prevent human infections. Specific vaccination recommendations are under the remit of national authorities (EFSA, ECDC and EURL).

Aflunov is currently the only vaccine authorised in humans against avian influenza (zoonotic pre-pandemic vaccine). It has a virus component of a previous, outdated virus clade and is an inactivated and adjuvanted H5N1 vaccine. (More information on EMA page)

The Health Emergency Preparedness and Response (HERA) department of the European Commission manages two joint procurement contracts of egg-based pandemic influenza vaccines for the EU countries. These are to be activated following the declaration of influenza pandemic by the WHO or if an influenza pandemic is declared a public health emergency at the level of the EU.

6.5 After exposure measures

People who have been exposed to animals infected with avian influenza while not wearing appropriate personal protective equipment should be monitored for symptoms for 10–14 days after the last exposure and tested if symptoms develop. Testing can also be considered in individuals without symptoms following exposure to infected animals.

If people develop symptoms (e.g. fever, conjunctivitis, diarrhoea, respiratory, neurological, or other atypical symptoms), immediate testing should be performed. People should isolate at home if the symptoms do not require hospitalisation. Contacts of confirmed cases also need to be tested and monitored to rule out further spread.

People in the EU presenting with severe acute respiratory or influenza-like infection and a history of exposure to poultry or wild animals will require careful investigation, management and infection control. Appropriate samples for influenza tests should be rapidly taken and processed from patients with relevant exposure history within 10-14 days preceding the symptom onset. If positive specimens cannot be subtyped, those should be shared with the national reference laboratory (National Influenza Centres; NICs). With routine diagnostic laboratory assays, human infection with A(H5Nx) viruses should be detected as positive for influenza A virus, and negative for influenza B, A(H1), A(H1)pdm09 and A(H3) viruses and therefore classified as unsubtyped influenza A virus, if no specific A(H5) diagnostic test is performed. Such unsubtyped influenza A virus isolates or clinical samples that cannot be subtyped should be sent to NICs, and further to a WHO. The confirmation of a true avian influenza infection in a person following a positive PCR should include repeated testing to exclude a false-positive signal, subsequent virus sequencing to produce full-length genomes for further analysis, virus cultivation, and material should be shared with reference laboratories and WHO-CCs for virus characterisation as outlined in the guidance document about testing and detection of zoonotic influenza virus infections in humans in the EU/EEA, and occupational safety and health measures for those exposed at work. Also, serological investigations are needed to identify seroconversion for case ascertainment (ECDC, 2022c).

AIV are susceptible to antivirals. Even when treatment is initiated beyond the initial 48-h window, it has been demonstrated to reduce the mortality risk in severely ill patients (Muthuri et al., 2013). Post-exposure prophylaxis can be considered for persons exposed to infected animals (even without symptoms) and for contacts of probable or confirmed human cases. (EFSA and ECDC, 2024).

6.6. Continuous assessment of the zoonotic risk requires sharing of sequences

Although there is no indication of an increased risk of avian influenza transmission to humans at present based on available epidemiological and sequencing data, the risk assessment should be reviewed regularly, taking into consideration any new developments and information becoming available. National authorities should remain vigilant for potential human cases of avian influenza, especially in geographical areas where the virus is known to occur in poultry and wild animals.

Reporting Human infections with avian influenza viruses are notifiable under EU legislation within 24 hours through the Early Warning and Response System (EWRS) according to EU Decision 1082/2013/EU9. Reporting is also required through the International Health Regulations (IHR) notification system (WHO, 2017).

The timely characterisation of viruses and the sharing of sequence information remain crucial for the monitoring of virus evolution and for virus vaccine development. Sharing of sequence data through the GISAID EpiFlu (GSAID, online) or other sequence databases and of virus isolates with WHO Collaborating Centres are important for public health assessment, improvement of diagnostics and the development of candidate vaccines. Sharing of influenza viruses occurs through the Global Influenza Surveillance and Response System (GISRS) (WHO, online-b).

6.7. Candidate vaccine viruses for pandemic preparedness

The WHO lists Candidate vaccine viruses (CVV) which have been developed, are under development or proposed. A new H5 clade 2.3.4.4b virus CVV (A/American wigeon/South Carolina/22-000345-001/2021) has been proposed during the Vaccine Composition Meeting for the Northern Hemisphere in February 2023(link is external) that is antigenically more similar to the recently circulating avian influenza H5 viruses in the US.

There are no indications at the present time that currently circulating avian influenza A(H5N1) viruses in the EU/EEA in birds differ antigenically from developed candidate vaccine viruses of previously circulating A(H5) viruses in Europe.

6.8. Legislation on occupational health and safety measures

An extensive set of legislation in the EU to protect workers from health and safety risks are available in accordance with occupational health and safety legislation. Measures at the workplace may include physical distancing, enhanced ventilation, dust- and aerosol-avoiding measures (for example, when cleaning and handling litter), and using appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE). Detailed information on occupational safety and health in the workplace has been outlined in the September–December 2022 avian influenza overview report, jointly authored by EFSA, ECDC and EURL (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7786>)

Some examples of EU legislation are:

Directive 2000/54/EC on the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to biological agents at work

Directive 89/391/EEC on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work (the Framework Directive)

Directive 89/656/EEC on the minimum health and safety requirements for the use by workers of personal protective equipment at the workplace

Regulation (EU) 2016/425 on personal protective equipment

7. Conclusions

An efficient way to find disease is to survey the animal populations that are most likely to be affected, i.e., to perform risk-based surveillance. Unfortunately, dynamics of HPAI adaptation and circulation within wild mammal populations (i.e. how the virus may evolve to infect new hosts, the ecological interactions between birds and mammals, and the specific factors that influence transmission in the environments) are not yet fully understood. As there is a lack of studies that have formally identified risk factors and calculated or estimated relative risk values for HPAIV spill-over events to mammals (bird-to-mammal and mammal-to-mammal), surveillance schemes for HPAIV in mammals rely on mammal case reports and outbreak reports to identify epidemiological drivers, and on making parallels with known risk factors for birds, poultry and humans. To date, most cases have concerned wild carnivores and mammals living in the aquatic environment.

Based on the identified drivers and on the overview of clinical signs and pathology, three epidemiological scenarios stood out for passive surveillance: 1) animals evidencing clinical signs compatible with HPAI, namely neurological and/or respiratory signs; 2) Sick or dead mammals close to confirmed or suspected HPAI outbreaks in birds and/or mammals; 3) animals showing another epidemiological connection with suspected or confirmed cases of HPAI in birds or mammals, such as sharing waterbird habitat. Even if wild bird disease hotspots seem to be an important driver for infection of free-living mammals during epidemics, many mammal HPAI cases occur in a spotted way. Therefore, every mammal with neurological signs or abnormal behaviour (especially carnivores that represent almost 90% of HPAI cases in mammals) must be considered as suspect in an HPAIV context. Convenience sampling as a form of active surveillance can provide information not only on-going but also on past HPAIV infections in wild mammal populations, key information for understanding HPAIV epidemiology in mammals. Surveillance should include not only diagnosis but also whole genome sequencing of virus and identification of markers for mammalian adaptation for all mammal cases.

The management of HPAI outbreaks in wild mammals requires a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach integrating not only the monitoring of virus circulation, but also the implementation of control strategies in collaboration with official institutions at national and international scale and relevant stakeholders. Also, the great variability of epidemiological scenarios in which HPAI outbreaks can occur (e.g. wild environments, farms, zoos, etc.) strongly influences the control strategies to be followed in mammals.

Wild birds and mammals carcass search and removal would help prevent carnivores and scavengers feeding on them and, consequently, spreading of the disease or triggering spill-over events to mammals. The use of tools such as the iMammalia app (<https://enetwild.com/resources/our-tools/>) could be of great help in signaling sick or dead mammals allowing detection of cases from one side and removal of potential source of infection from the other.

A comprehensive knowledge of free-ranging or farmed wildlife in parks, zoos, and rescue centres, including the species abundance and their spatial distribution, is crucial for the precise targeting of biosecurity measures, and to tailor preparedness strategies to the specific characteristics of animal populations and allow a rapid response planning. This includes, for captive settings (zoos, farms, rehabilitation centers) a detailed record of species kept in the facilities, and, for free-ranging species, reliable and detailed information on their abundance and spatial distribution across the whole continent.

Considering that HPAI in wild mammals involves a complex network of stakeholders (i.e. various ministries, veterinary authorities, wildlife managers, farm workers, and associations representing those who work in zoos and rehabilitation centres as well as the general public) and given the diverse nature of these groups, it is essential to create and consolidate a network in “time of peace” to ensure efficient communication, coordination, and action in the surveillance or during an outbreak. A good communication strategy is also important to assure the collaboration and support of the general public to the implementation of effective control measures.

In the context of captive mammals, it is advisable to minimise contact between different species to prevent spill-over events through strict biosecurity measures designed to keep species separate or by avoiding the co-habitation of multiple species within the same facility. Feed can be a source of infection and to reduce risk it may need to be either replaced with less risky products or properly inactivated.

In conclusion, we identified drivers of infection as proxys for risk factors triggering HPAIV spill-over events to mammals, knowledge of which needs to be further substantiated. We determined clinical signs and pathology associated with HPAIV infection in wild mammals. Collectively this information orients efficient passive surveillance scenarios. However, there is a bias towards fatal infections and there is a need for more general information on non-fatal infections, to which active surveillance can contribute. Control and prevention measures can be partially based on existing guidelines and protocols but still need to be tailored towards the risk of HPAIV in wild mammals. Good communication with all stakeholders is paramount for success.

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Annex – Clinical signs, gross pathology and histopathology of HPAI natural infection in mammals

FAMILY - Species	Year	Country	HPAIV	Clinical signs	Gross pathology	Histopathology	Reference
CANIDAE – Artic fox (<i>Vulpes lagopus</i>)	2023	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	See <i>multiple species</i>		Bronchointerstitial pneumonia (23/27) Meningoencephalitis (13/18) Liver necrosis (18/26) Peritonitis (19/24) Splenic lymphoid depletion (10/24)	Kareinen et al., 2024
CANIDAE - Coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Ataxia, lethargy	See below (<i>multiple species</i>)	See below (<i>multiple species</i>)	Elsmo et al., 2023
CANIDAE - Gray fox (<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Ataxia, lack of fear, circling	See below (<i>multiple species</i>)	See below (<i>multiple species</i>)	Elsmo et al., 2023
CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2021	UK	H5N8	Malaise, inappetence	Poor body condition Generalized reddening of the lungs Mild splenomegaly Alopecia and crusts affecting the skin of the body and limbs	Severe, acute, necrotizing, nonsuppurative interstitial pneumonia, Severe, acute, nonsuppurative, polio-encephalitis and ventriculitis and Mild, acute, nonsuppurative myocarditis	Floyd et al 2021

HPAI in mammals

CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2021	NL	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Laboured breathing Lip retraction, rapid opening and closing of mouth, skin twitching, head shaking, and body tremors, difficult swallowing, excessive salivation	-	-	Rijks et al 2021
CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2021	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	-	Good condition. Heavy, oedematous and dark red lungs 1 of 2 also blood-tinged transudate in thoracic cavity. Empty stomachs	Severe acute multifocal necrotizing pneumonia and Acute haemorrhages in the liver and kidneys. No abnormalities in the brain.	Tamiranta et al. 2023
CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2021, 2022	NL	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	lethargy, crouching down with convex back and legs tucked under, Blindness, head shaking, falling over, opisthotonos; convulsions; lacked fleeing behaviour but alert	Moderate to poor body condition. Poorly collapsed lungs with a marbled red aspect (note: was not associated with virus protein expression)	Nonsuppurative encephalitis with perivascular cuffing, Subacute lymphoplasmacytic myocarditis with myocardial degeneration and necrosis	Bordes et al. 2023

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CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Lethargy (20/44), fever (5/44), unconsciousness (3/44), recumbence (1/44) Dyspnoea (1/44) Neurologic abnormalities (40/44), comprising seizures (23/44), ataxia (17/44), tremors (10/44), lack of fear of humans (3/44), vocalization (5/44), circling (3/44), blindness (3/44), torticollis (2/44), nystagmus (1/44), grimace (1/44), paralysis (1/44), hypersalivation (5/44). Diarrhoea (2/44) and vomiting (1/44), and	<i>See: multiple species</i>	<i>See: multiple species</i>	Elsmo et al., 2023
CANIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2023	Canada	H5N5 clade 2.3.4.4b	Disorientation, and barely walking	-	-	Erdelyan et al. 2024
CANIDAE - Silver fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	2023	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	<i>See multiple species</i>		Bronchointerstitial pneumonia (0/1) Meningoencephalitis (not examined) Liver necrosis (1/1) Peritonitis (0/1) Splenic lymphoid depletion (1/1)	Kareinen et al., 2024

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DIDELPHIDAE - Opossum (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Seizures (2/2)	<i>See: multiple species</i>	<i>See: multiple species</i>	Elsmo et al., 2023
FELIDAE - Bobcat (<i>Lynx rufus</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Lethargy (1/2) Dyspnoea (1/2) Neurologic abnormalities (2/2), comprising tremors (1/2), lack of fear (2/2)	<i>See: multiple species</i>	<i>See: multiple species</i>	Elsmo et al., 2023
FELIDAE - Eurasian Lynx (<i>Lynx lynx</i>)	2021	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	-	Normal body condition but markedly dehydrated. Lungs were dark red, mottled, swollen and oedematous Petechial haemorrhages in the muscles, subcutaneous tissues and multiple organs	Severe necrotizing pneumonia Multifocal acute haemorrhages in the heart and lungs	Tammiranta et al. 2023
FELIDAE - Tigers (<i>Panthera tigris</i>)	2004	Thailand	H5N1	High fever and Respiratory distress, serosanguinous nasal discharge Some had neurologic signs of infection	The lungs were severely congested and had been hemorrhaging. Sero-sanguinous exudate was seen throughout the tracheal and bronchiolar lumen, and pleural effusion was also seen.	Severe diffuse lung hemorrhage and edema, Moderate congestion of the brain with mild nonsuppurative meningoencephalitis Moderate multifocal necrotizing hepatitis	Thanawongnuwech et al, 2005

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MEPHITIDAE - Striped skunk (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Lethargy (5/5) Dyspnoea (2/5 animals). Neurologic abnormalities (5/5), comprising tremors (5/5), seizures (3/5), and ataxia (1/5)	<i>See: multiple species</i>	<i>See: multiple species</i>	Elsmo et al., 2023
MUSTELIDAE - American mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>)	2022	Spain	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Loss of appetite, depression, Bloody snout Neurological manifestations such as ataxia and tremors, hypersalivation	'Haemorrhagic pneumonia or red hepatisation of the lungs'		Aguero et al 2023
MUSTELIDAE - American mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>)	2023	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	<i>See multiple species</i>		Bronchointerstitial pneumonia (2/6) Meningoencephalitis (1/1) Liver necrosis (5/5) Peritonitis (0/5) Splenic lymphoid depletion (3/5)	Kareinen et al., 2024
MUSTELIDAE - Eurasian otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)	2021	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Tremors and convulsions	Poor body condition Swollen lungs mottled with small petechiae	Severe multifocal hemorrhagic and necrotizing pneumonia in the lungs, Moderate nonsuppurative necrotizing meningoencephalitis in the cerebrum and brainstem, and	Tammiranta et al. 2023

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						Severe multifocal necrotizing pancreatitis	
MUSTELIDAE - Fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Lethargy Ataxia, lack of fear	<i>See: multiple species</i>	<i>See: multiple species</i>	Elsmo et al., 2023
MUSTELIDAE - Stone marten (<i>Martes foina</i>)	2006	Germany	H5N1	Depression, Ataxia, circling	Moderate emaciation, Mild swelling of the retropharyngeal lymph nodes and Scattered pinpoint white foci in both kidneys	Diffuse nonsuppurative panencephalitis with perivascular cuffing, multifocal gliosis and neuronal necrosis. Additionally, focal necrosis of pancreatic acinar cells	Klopfleisch et al, 2007
OTARIIDAE - South American sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>)	2023	Peru	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Respiratory signs such as dyspnea, tachypnea and nasal secretions Mainly neurological signs such as tremors, convulsions and paralysis, and buccal secretions	Good to very good body condition. Substantial quantities of whitish secretions filling the upper respiratory tract (trachea and pharynx). Lungs were congestive, with hemorrhagic focus compatible with interstitial pneumonia. Brain was also congestive, with hemorrhagic focus compatible with encephalitis	Acute pneumonia and Encephalitis	Gamarra-Toledo et al, 2023
OTARIIDAE - South American sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>)	2023	Argentina	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Difficulty breathing, Inability to stand or walk, muscular tremors and spasms and abundant oral mucus	-	-	Rimondi et al., 2024

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PHOCIDAE - Gray seal (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>)	2021	UK	H5N8	Sudden onset of fever, Facial twitching and stupor	Fair body condition, Generalized lymphadenomegaly	Severe, necrotizing, nonsuppurative polioencephalitis	Floyd et al 2021
PHOCIDAE - Gray seal (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>)	2022	NL	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Reluctance to dive (1 of 2) Laboured breathing Ataxia, body tremors Anorexia (1 of 2)	Good body condition (1 of 2). Lungs: dark-red colouration (2 of 2), failure to collapse, diffuse firmness (1 of 2); Hyperplastic lymph nodes, moderate thymic atrophy, fibrinous perisplenitis and catarrhal enteritis	Multifocal mild to moderate non-suppurative interstitial pneumonia with lymphohistiocytic vasculitis (1 of 2) Multi focal moderate to severe lymphohistiocytic and necrotising (meningo-)encephalitis (2 of 2). Note: Intralésional nucleoprotein antigen of AIV was detected only in the brain of this animal	Mirolo et al. 2023
PHOCIDAE - Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)	2021	UK	H5N8	Seizures (sudden onset)	Fair body condition, Generalized lymphadenomegaly Multiple pale foci in the lungs. One common seal also showed congested meninges.	Mild, eosinophilic, interstitial pneumonia in the 2 common seals, consistent with lungworm infection, and Severe, necrotizing, nonsuppurative polioencephalitis	Floyd et al 2021
PHOCIDAE - Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)	2021	Germany	H5N8 clade 2.3.4.4b	Lethargic with no signs of reaction		Severe, diffuse, acute hyperemia of the lung and an alveolar emphysema and oedema Mild to moderate necrotic and lymphohistiocytic meningoencephalitis with few neutrophils and haemorrhage	Postel et al 2021

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PHOCOENIDAE - Harbour porpoise (<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>)	2022	Sweden	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Swam in circles, was unable to right itself	Minimal and included pulmonary edema consistent with drowning	The lung contained few areas of mild, mononuclear septal thickening and increased numbers of alveolar macrophages. Lymphoplasmacytic meningoencephalitis with neuronal necrosis, gliosis, perivascular cuffing, and vasculitis in the brain.	Thorsson et al. 2023
PROCYONIDAE - Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Neurologic abnormalities, including in 1 of 2 with ataxia	-	-	Elsmo et al, 2024
VIVERRIDAE -Owston's civet (<i>Chrotogale owstoni</i>)	2006	Vietnam	H5N1	Appetite loss Neurological symptoms, including convulsions, hind limb paralysis	Pulmonary oedema	Pulmonary oedema with mild parenchymal inflammation without evidence of hyaline membrane formation. Moderately severe meningitis was present, together with cerebral oedema and hypoxic change of the neurons. Foci of necrosis were seen in the liver	Robertson et al 2006
Multiple species: CANIDAE & MUSTELIDAE - Red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), polecat (<i>Mustela putorius</i>), badger (<i>Meles meles</i>), otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)	2022	NL	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	-	Poorly collapsed, red or marbled red lungs Nematode infestation with a variable associated subacute to chronic pneumonia	Non-suppurative meningitis, encephalitis, or meningoencephalitis with variation in severity from mild to severe and most prominent in the cerebrum	Vreman et al., 2023

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<p>Multiple species: CANIDAE, DIDELPHIDAE, FELIDAE, MEPHITIDAE, MUSTELIDAE & PROCYONIDAE - 1 coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>), 1 gray fox (<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>) 50 red foxes (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), 2 Virginia opossums (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>), 2 bobcats (<i>Lynx rufus</i>), 6 striped skunks (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>), 1 fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>), 4 raccoons (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)</p>	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	<i>Detailed per species.</i>	<p>Fair to good nutritional condition.</p> <p>Lung lesions, congestion, edema, failure to collapse, hemorrhage, and pleural effusion.</p> <p>Brain lesions were hemorrhage and congestion.</p> <p>Other lesions included pallor, congestion, enlargement, hemorrhage in the liver, congestion and cortical hemorrhage in the kidney, and pericardial effusion, petechia, myocardial pallor</p> <p>In the gastrointestinal tract, nematode parasitism was relatively common (n = 15), but other rarely observed lesions included congestion, hemorrhage, and loose feces.</p> <p>Mild ocular discharge in three red foxes</p> <p>Severe haemorrhages in all body cavities in the grey fox</p>	<p>The most common lesions were:</p> <p>Interstitial pneumonia, Necrotizing meningoencephalitis, and Myocardial necrosis</p>	Elsmo et al., 2023
<p>Multiple species: CANIDAE, MUSTELIDAE & PROCYONIDAE - 1 coyote (<i>Canis</i> Farmed foxes (artic blue fox</p>	2023	Finland	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	<p>Anorexia (15/26 farms) Respiratory symptoms (2/16),</p>	-	<i>See individual species</i>	Kareinen et al., 2024

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(<i>Vulpes lagopus</i>), the red (silver) fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>), fox crossbreeds), mink (<i>Neogale vison</i>), and raccoon dog (<i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i>)				Neurological symptoms (18/26), apathy (6/26), Diarrhoea (4/26) Mortality (22/26), No clinical signs and normal mortality (1/26)			
Multiple species: DELPHINIDAE & OTARIIDAE - South American sea lion (<i>Otaria flavescens</i>), common dolphin (<i>Delphinus delphis</i>)	2022	Peru	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Copious nasal discharge, dyspnea Disorientation, ataxia, circling, "stargazing" position, seizures, sialorrhea	-	-	Leguia et al 2023
Multiple species: FELIDAE - Tigers (<i>Panthera tigris</i>), leopards (<i>Panthera pardus</i>)	2003	Thailand	H5N1	High fever and Respiratory distress	Severe pulmonary consolidation and Multifocal haemorrhage in several organs, including lung, heart, thymus, stomach, intestine, liver, and lymph nodes.	Pulmonary lesions were characterized by loss of bronchiolar and alveolar epithelium; thickening of alveolar walls; and flooding of alveolar lumens with oedema fluid mixed with fibrin, erythrocytes, neutrophils, and macrophages. Encephalitis, characterized by multifocal infiltration by neutrophils and macrophages	Keawcharoen et al 2004
Multiple species: PHOCIDAE - Gray seal (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>) & Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)	2022	USA	H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b	Respiratory symptoms, With a subset of neurologic cases	-	-	Puryear et al 2023